

CANCER
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GRAND
CHALLENGE
MUTOGRAPHS

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*Discover how unusual patterns of mutation
are induced by different cancer-causing events*

Mutographs of cancer:

**discovering the causes of cancer
through mutational signatures**

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)

Mutational signatures in five cancer types across five continents

Parts of these SOPs were based on, and adapted from, the “Common Minimum Technical Standards and Protocols for Biological Resource Centres dedicated to Cancer Research” (WHO-IARC, WorkGroup Report 2, and IARC Technical publication No. 44 IARC, 2007& 2017), the Canadian Tumor Repository Network procedures (<http://www.ctrnet.ca/>), the cancer protocol templates from the College of American Pathologists (<http://www.cap.org>), the WHO Classification of Tumors, 5th edition, and the American joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) 8th edition.

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I. Overview and aim of the study

Over the last century, we have learnt much about the environmental, lifestyle, genetic and other factors that cause human cancer. This knowledge has provided the foundation for successful cancer prevention programmes including, among many others, those aimed at reducing tobacco smoking, eradicating carcinogenic viruses, eliminating environmental and industrial exposures such as radiation and asbestos, and reducing breast and ovarian cancer in women with high inherited risk. However, many common cancers exhibit major differences in incidence between different geographical areas and trends over time for which we do not understand the reasons despite determined investigation. Therefore, important causes of cancer and opportunities for prevention remain to be identified.

All cancers are caused by changes in the DNA of cells in the body that occur over the course of an individual's lifetime. These changes are called somatic mutations. Different patterns of somatic mutation, known as "mutational signatures", are generated by the different environmental, lifestyle and genetic factors that cause cancer. For example, tobacco smoke and ultraviolet radiation in sunlight both cause cancer by generating somatic mutations, but different mutational signatures are found in the lung and skin cancers that they respectively cause. Recently, through analysis of the DNA sequences of many thousands of cancers of diverse types from across the world, more than 40 different mutational signatures have been reported. However, the environmental, lifestyle, genetic or other potential causes of many of these mutational signatures are unknown.

A major aim of the *mutographs* project is to advance our understanding of the causes of cancer through studies of mutational signatures. This will involve investigating mutational signatures on more than 6000 individuals with cancer for 8 different cancer types across 5 continents. By conducting whole genome sequencing of the tumor from all 6000 patients, we will explore whether different mutational signatures in the DNA of cancers explain geographic differences in cancer incidence. We will also identify the specific causes of mutational signatures, be they lifestyle or environmental. Through understanding the causes of cancer, our work may lead to new approaches to prevent it and could also provide opportunities for better treatment.

The current document presents in detail the overall protocol for collection and processing of biosamples and clinical data of the *mutographs* project. The document is meant to be a practical guidance for centres participating in this project.

Overall Aim: To elucidate the causes of major global geographical differences in cancer incidence through study of mutational signatures.

The cancer types to be studied

The five major classes of cancer that we will study are shown in Table 1. All show substantial geographical differences in cancer incidence that are largely unexplained despite extensive previous investigation. Lifestyle related factors associated with 'westernization' including obesity, hypertension, diabetes, excessive alcohol consumption and meat consumption are suspected of driving these international differences,

although evidence is often either limited or lacking. Some of the differences may also be dependent on particular local exposures.

Table 1: Areas with high and low incidence (standardized rates per 100,000) for five cancer types (source: IARC Cancer Incidence in Five Continents Volume X).

	Low incidence regions (male/female rates)	High incidence regions (male/female rates)	Main known or suspected protective (P) or risk (R) lifestyle-related or environmental factors (WCRF and IARC evaluations)
Colorectal (C18-20)	South Africa (1.7/1.0) Uganda (7.7/6.6) Morocco (9.9/7.3) Colombia (13.4/12.5)	Canada Ontario (40.7/27.5) Czech Republic (57.0/28.5) Japan (42.1/23.5) Brazil (29.5/26.6)	(P) Physical activity, fiber-rich diet (R) Red meat, processed meat, alcohol, BMI, diabetes
Kidney (C64)	Japan (7.8/3.0) Brazil, Sao Paulo (6.5/3.1)	Czech Republic (22.1/9.9) Slovakia (15.1/7.5) Lithuania (20.5/8.2)	(P) Alcohol (R) BMI, smoking, hypertension, workplace exposure
Pancreas (C25)	Iran, Golestan (2.8, 1.0) Uganda (2.7, 1.2) Brazil, Sao Paolo (5.2/4.2)	Czech Republic (11.6/ 7.5) Slovakia (11.2/6.4) Japan Miyagi (10.5/6.2)	(R) Smoking, BMI, diabetes
Oesophageal squamous cancer (C15)	Morocco (1.2/1.0) Canada, Ontario (4.4/1.2) Colombia (1.1/0.2)	Kenya (19.3/14.3) Uganda (23.3/ 9.8) Iran, Golestan (23.2/ 18.8) Japan (10.5/1.6) Brazil Porte Alegre (8.1/2.1)	(P) Vegetarian diet (R) Smoking, BMI, alcohol, hot drinks
Oesophageal adenocarcinoma (C15)	Iran, Tehran (0.9/0.9) Russia (0.8/0.1) Poland (0.5/0.1)	United Kingdom (7.2/1.4) Iran, Golestan (29/6) Ontario (3.0/0.4) Brazil (2.0/0.6)	(R) BMI (P) Physical activity

For each cancer type, we will aim to recruit cancer patients from a network of cancer centres in high and low incidence regions around the world including Europe, South America, Africa, Canada and Asia, collecting high quality tumor and peri-tumor samples together with blood samples and relevant epidemiological and clinical information. We will conduct whole genome sequencing of both tumor and blood DNA for these 6,000 sample pairs in order to identify somatic mutations. The mutation signatures present in each tumor will be identified and we will look for differences in the contributions of mutational signatures in order to inform on the reasons for differences in incidence.

Three other cancer sites have been added to the project: carcinoma of the gallbladder, urothelial carcinoma, and head & neck cancers to explore specific aetiologies in these cancers.

The study is currently expanding geographically to include additional cases of renal and colorectal cancers from centres already contributing to the study, as well as establishing new collaborations in other regions and countries.

Recruitment of cases

A major undertaking of the project is the recruitment of at least 6,000 cases for the eight cancer types across five continents according to strict protocols that will ensure collection of high-quality biological samples together with appropriate and reliable clinical and risk factor information. This will be achieved by contributions from 24 countries through a network of 30 cancer and academic centres (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Countries contributing samples and information to *mutographs*

We will aim to recruit between 1,500 and 2,000 cases of each cancer type as, based on previous experience, we expect to lose up to a third of cases at the tumor validation stage (see [chapter XII](#)).

II. Patient recruitment and clinical, demographical, lifestyle and outcome data collection

Where: Participating hospitals and cancer centres

Who: Hospital staff or research team

What: Consent form, and clinical, demographical, lifestyle and outcome data

How: Interview with the patient, abstract from medical records, cancer registries, etc.

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures for case recruitment and collection of clinical data to eliminate the discrepancies between centres. All information is collected from patients that have given their specific consent to participate in the *mutographs* project, or their general consent to participate to parallel research studies when the consent provided is consistent with the research activities foreseen in *mutographs*. Ongoing recruitment or retrospective collections can contribute to *mutographs* if the followed protocol is consistent with these guidelines.

Prospective recruitment of all cases will take place according to the following strategy:

- i. The case is identified and their eligibility to the study is confirmed;
- ii. The case is informed of the study and if they agree to participate, they are requested to complete the informed consent form ([Appendix 2](#));
- iii. A lifestyle questionnaire is administered to the case individual by a trained interview (using lifestyle questionnaire and questionnaire manual in [Appendix 3](#));
- iv. Anthropometric measures are taken from the case (height, weight, blood pressure) and additional clinical information is collected from the clinical notes (see [Appendix 4](#));
- v. A blood sample is obtained from the case individual. When feasible, this is a fasting blood sample. Details are recorded in [Appendix 5](#);
- vi. A tumor and non tumor tissue sampling is performed and preserved frozen. Details are recorded in [Appendix 5](#).

2. Case recruitment

Approach of patients

Patients aged 18 or more should be approached when a cancer diagnosis is suspected, and routine medical care begins. Early identification is possible only through active search, i.e., by means of periodical visits to the hospital departments where cases are diagnosed or treated (e.g., urology, gastroenterology, oncology,

surgery, radiotherapy and pathology). The frequency of the visits (daily, weekly etc.) will depend on the cancer burden of each department.

Following the collection of informed consent, patients will be interviewed, and biological samples taken, pending subsequent histological confirmation. Anthropometric and blood pressure measures will be taken during clinical consultation with a doctor or a nurse following the protocol provided in [Appendix 4](#). Other clinical information requested in [Appendix 4](#) will be filled in by the doctor or abstracted from clinical notes.

Informed consent

Eligible patients will be asked to read and sign a consent form, which describes the study background and explain the procedures. Each participating centre will be responsible for archiving participants' consent forms ([Appendix 2](#)).

Case ascertainment

Patients will be considered for inclusion if they have a pathological diagnosis of a primary invasive carcinoma of one of the five different types as defined in the Table 2 according to the International Classification for Diseases in Oncology (ICD-O-3 First revision, 2011, <https://www.who.int/standards/classifications/other-classifications/international-classification-of-diseases-for-oncology>).

Although several criteria might be developed to prioritize samples that will be sequenced within *mutographs* (e.g., histological subtypes, cases with no familial history and no defined genetic predisposition), all cases that fall into the minimum eligibility criteria listed below shall be recruited and biobanked upon consent:

Minimum eligibility criteria:

Cases must be at least 18 years old.

Cases of primary kidney, urothelial tract, pancreatic, colorectal, and oesophageal carcinoma. They must be incident cases (newly diagnosed or diagnosed within the previous 6 months). NB: Cases may have been diagnosed for the first time outside the participating study hospitals but must be recruited before treatment has started.

Pathological confirmation of the cancer as primary cancer is requested (see [chapter VI](#)). NB: Cases with previous primary tumours (including of same site) are not excluded, although this should be reported in the medical history.

Exclusion criteria

Patients are excluded if there is no means of obtaining an adequate tissue as per the protocol requirements.

Patients are excluded if they have any condition that could interfere with their ability to provide informed consent such as dementia or severe cognitive impairment.

Table 2: Eligible topographical and histological codes for each cancer type.

Cancer type: common name (specific name)	Topographical codes	Histological codes	Notes
Kidney cancer (renal cell carcinoma)	C64: Kidney C64.9: Kidney, NOS	8310/3: Clear cell renal cell carcinoma 8260/3: Papillary renal cell carcinoma 8317/3: Chromophobe renal cell carcinoma 8319/3: Collecting duct carcinoma 8510/3: Renal medullary carcinoma 8316/3: Tubulocystic renal cell carcinoma 8312/3: Renal cell carcinoma, NOS	Mesenchymal and, Oncocytic tumors, (such as oncocytoma and angiomyolipoma) lymphomas and NEN ¹ are ² excluded from this study. This EXCLUDES the following topographies: C65 (renal pelvis) C66 (ureter) C68 (urethra)
Pancreatic cancer (pancreatic exocrine tumor)	C25.0: Head of pancreas C25.1: Body of pancreas C25.2: Tail of pancreas C25.7: Neck of pancreas C25.8: Overlapping lesions of pancreas C25.9: Pancreas, unspecified	8500/3: Ductal ADC ³ 8560/3: Adenosquamous carcinoma 8480/3: Colloid carcinoma 8576/3: Hepatoid carcinoma 8510/3: Medullary carcinoma 8490/3: Signet ring cell carcinoma 8020/3: Undifferentiated carcinoma	This EXCLUDES the following topographies: C25.3 (pancreatic duct) C25.4 (endocrine pancreas) This EXCLUDES the following morphologies: mesenchymal tumours, lymphomas, NEN ¹ , and non-ductal carcinomas, including pancreatic acinar cell carcinoma and solid pseudopapillary neoplasm of the pancreas
Colorectal cancer	C18: Colon (any subsite) C19: Rectosigmoid junction C20: Rectum	8140/3: ADC 8510/3: Medullary carcinoma 8265/3: Micropapillary carcinoma 8480/3: Mucinous carcinoma 8213/3: Serrated ADC 8490/3: Poorly cohesive/Signet ring carcinoma 8560/3: Adenosquamous carcinoma	This EXCLUDES the following morphologies: mesenchymal tumours, lymphomas, and NEN ¹ .

		8070/3: SCC ⁴ 8020/3: Undifferentiated carcinoma 8262/3: Adenoma-like ADC	
Oesophageal squamous cell carcinoma	C15.-: Oesophagus (any subsite)	8070/3: SCC ⁴ 8051/3: Verrucous (squamous) carcinoma 8083/3: Basaloid SCC ⁴ 8074/3: Spindle cell (squamous) carcinoma 8020/3: Undifferentiated carcinoma	N/A
Esophageal adenocarcinoma and carcinomas of the gastroesophageal junction	C15.-: Oesophagus (any subsite) C16.0: Gastroesophageal junction (GEJ) and Gastric cardia	8140/3: ADC ³	This EXCLUDES Siewert type III sub-cardial gastric carcinoma infiltrating the esophagogastric junction
Tumours of the urothelial tract (Urinary bladder, renal pelvis, ureter, and urethra)	C65: Renal pelvis; C65.9: Pelvis of kidney, renal calyces; C66 & C66.9: Ureter; C67: Urinary Bladder; C67.0: Trigone of bladder; C67.1: Dome of bladder; C67.2: Lateral wall of bladder; C67.3: Anterior wall of bladder; C67.4: Posterior wall of bladder; C67.5: Bladder neck; C67.6: Ureteric orifice; C67.7: Urachus; C67.8: Overlapping lesion of bladder; C67.9: Bladder, NOS C68: Other and unspecified urinary organs; C68.0: Urethra; C68.1: Paraurethral gland; C68.8: Overlapping lesion of urinary organs; C68.9: Urinary system, NOS	8120/3: Infiltrating urothelial carcinoma (IUC) 8131/3: IUC, micropapillary 8082/3: IUC, lymphoepithelioma like 8122/3: IUC, Sarcomatoid 8031/3: IUC, Giant cell 8020/3: IUC, poorly differentiated 8130/3: IUC, Papillary 8120/2: Urothelial carcinoma in situ 8130/1: Papillary urothelial neoplasm of low malignant potential 8130/2: Papillary urothelial carcinoma, non-invasive 8070/3: Squamous cell carcinoma 8051/3: Verrucous carcinoma 8140/3: Adenocarcinoma, NOS	Mesenchymal tumours, lymphomas and NEN ¹ are excluded from this study.

¹NEN: Neuroendocrine Neoplasms containing both NET (Neuroendocrine Tumours) and NEC (Neuroendocrine Cracinoma)

²Excluded morphologies might become eligible in specific projects according to project-specific inclusion criteria

³ADC: Adenocarcinoma

⁴SCC: Squamous cell carcinoma.

⁵Only junctional tumors classified as esophageal or junctional by endoscopists.

Timeline

The official start of the study was May 2017, and recruitment of the initial series of cases from the main 5 cancer types is expected to be completed by year 2024 of the study. For the expansion of renal and colorectal cases, recruitment of this specific sites will take place until 2027, according to the following timetable:

Months 1-6: Establishing study, including obtaining all local and central ethical approvals, training of staff, translation of questionnaire and other material (if necessary), agreeing MTAs and DTAs

Months 7-12: Pilot study of recruitment, including evaluation of tumor material and blood viability

Months 7-15: Full evaluation of pilot study in each centre, and confirmation of planned recruitment for years 2-4

Years 2-7: Full completion of recruitment, shipping of all samples, completion of databases, short-term follow-up of cases

Years 7-10: Full completion of recruitment, shipping of all samples, completion of databases, short-term follow-up of additional colorectal and renal cancer cases

Year 5 onwards: Ongoing follow-up of cases.

3. Collection of clinical data, demographical and lifestyle data

Cases will be interviewed by trained interviewers using a lifestyle questionnaire, which includes a section on demographical data and a section on additional clinical data, such as hypertension, medical history, etc. ([Appendix 3](#)). Guidelines for interviewers can be found in ([Appendix 13](#)). Established and suspected risk factors, be they lifestyle, external exposure, or familial history, are included in the questionnaire. Information on the basis for the diagnosis, the patient clinical condition at diagnosis, the clinical staging of the cancer, and the first line treatment will be collected in the diagnosis and pathological data form ([Appendix 6](#))

4. Follow-up of cases: outcome and further clinical data

On a regular basis, follow-up data will be entered in the follow-up form, which includes vital status, tumor progression, primary and secondary cause of death, events occurring after diagnosis (local recurrence, metastasis, second primary cancer, others), and second line treatment ([Appendix 7](#)).

Centres will use active follow-up, passive follow-up, or both, depending on the possibility of access to local sources of data. The method(s) used for each patient will be specified in the follow-up form. Centres conducting active follow-up should make sure that the consent form contains the information that will help re-contacting the patient in the future (personal identification number, if applicable, address, phone number(s), medical record reference, and name of the physician who diagnosed/treated the cancer).

5. Archives and computerized data

Each case will be attributed with a unique, identification number (ID). Recruiting centres will be provided with barcoded labels as detailed in [Appendix 8](#). Link with the name and other personal information will only be available to authorized staff of the research team. Forms (hard copies) will be labelled with the corresponding ID and archived in local centres.

IARC will organize local computerization of data through web-based entry templates, which will also allow uploads of data in batches for retrospective collections or recruitment following own protocols and data entry systems. IARC will then centralize and process these data, to be linked with biosample-related data.

III. a Collection and processing of blood samples

Where: At patient's bed and local laboratory

Who: Hospital staff or research team technicians

What: Two blood samples

How: Processing to store buffy coat

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

Blood samples are drawn from patients that have been through the informed consent process and agreed to participate in the *mutographs* study. Blood samples are obtained by personnel qualified to draw blood from patients in the centre/hospital. The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures for *mutographs* study to follow for blood processing. This procedure is intended to ensure that blood samples will be obtained from consented participants in a safe and efficient manner while eliminating the risks of contamination and loss.

The Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) describes how blood should be processed, accessioned, and stored. The SOP does not cover detailed safety procedures for handling blood, and it is recommended that personnel follow institutional biosafety guidelines.

For *mutographs* (germline DNA extraction), this chapter covers whole blood and buffy coat collection and storage. For the purpose of a biobank in general, plasma collection is encouraged, and red blood cells and viable lymphocytes may be isolated and stored, although this goes beyond the goal of the current SOPs.

2. Material used

- Vacutainer tubes using EDTA as an anticoagulant (10 ml and 3 ml vacutainers)
- 2 ml cryotubes
- Pipettes
- -80°C freezer

Note: Each centre should contact IARC if they experience any problems in obtaining either Vacutainer tubes or cryotubes. These can be provided by IARC.

3. Blood extraction

Two samples of blood with EDTA should be obtained (10ml + 3ml). The first 10ml will be divided into plasma, leucocytes/platelets (buffy coat) and red blood cells (RBC). The second sample (3ml) will be stored as whole blood. Whenever possible, fasting blood would be preferred.

4. Blood processing

Blood samples can stay at 4°C for a maximum of 12 hours before being processed in a laboratory. Ideally, blood should be processed within 2 hours.

The protocol below describes blood processing for storage of whole blood, buffy coat, plasma, and RBC. Routine protocols of each centre might be used, if DNA extraction of the buffy coat fraction or from whole blood shows good yield (to be verified in pilot phase).

From the 3ml vacutainer:

- Do not centrifuge.
- Aliquot the whole blood into 2 cryotubes (2 ml) with brown top.

From the 10ml vacutainer, the following should be obtained:

- 3-4 tubes of plasma (2 ml tubes)
- 2 tube of buffy coat (2 ml tubes)
- 3-4 tubes of RBC (2 ml tubes)

The blood with EDTA is centrifuged for 10 minutes at 2000 x g (with acceleration and deceleration scores of 4). Three layers will be obtained. The upper layer (plasma) is generally clear and pale yellow in colour. The second layer is a narrow greyish white interface band representing the "buffy coat" fraction. The third or bottom layer is dark red and consists of the RBC.

Plasma

- Using an appropriate disposable transfer pipette, aspirate off the plasma layer (uppermost yellow layer, about 50-60% of the blood sample) down to approximately 1 mm from the buffy coat layer. Take care not to disturb the leukocyte or buffy coat layer.
- Aliquot recovered plasma into 3-4 different labelled cryovials with yellow tops.

Buffy coat

- After removing the plasma layer, use a transfer pipette to aspirate the entire buffy coat layer.
- Collect the top 2ml of the remaining specimen making sure that the buffy coat is included. Note that this layer is sometimes hard to visualize, which is why it is better to include some plasma and RBC.
- Expel the buffy coat into a single cryovial. If aliquots are needed, invert the tube 2-3 times to make it homogenous, and then divide into 2 separately labelled cryotubes, identified with white tops.

RBC

- After removing the buffy coat, use a transfer pipette to aspirate the remaining RBC layer.
- Aliquot recover RBC layer into 3-4 cryotubes with red tops.

If for any reason there is less blood than expected, do not fill as many tubes as requested.

Each tube will be labelled and coded with the subjects' full identification number ([Appendix 8](#)).

5. Storage

Store locally all obtained samples at -75 to -80°C. If possible, distribute them equally between different freezers to avoid the loss of material in case of any problem with one of the freezers (e.g. store whole blood in a separate freezer than processed samples). Enter storage location in your local tracking system and record the number and the type of stored samples in the database provided by IARC (see [Appendix 5](#)).

NOTE: *Optimal storage temperatures are -80°C or -190°C (liquid nitrogen). Storage in -20°C possible but is less favorable. If no other choice, store in -20°C and document the storage temperature.*

Periodically, samples will be shipped (see [Appendix 9](#) for shipment procedures) to IARC for central storage in IARC biobank, where they will be stored in liquid nitrogen tanks or -80°C freezers for long-term storage.

Enter storage location in a computerized database system.

6. Use of previously extracted DNA

It may happen that blood DNA of a *mutographs* eligible case is directly available (e.g., already extracted for the purpose of another project). Providing that the extraction protocol is validated by IARC and that the DNA materials passes quantity and quality controls detailed in [chapter VIII](#), the DNA may be used for sequencing. Please contact IARC staff to discuss applicability.

III. b Urine samples (not collected in the main *mutographs*)

Where: At patient's bed before surgery and local laboratory

Who: Hospital staff or research team technicians

What: One urine sample before surgery

How: Processing to store urine sample

1. Equipment and Material

- 50 ml centrifuge Falcon type conical tubes
- Urine Conditioning Buffer from Zymo Quick-DNA™ Urine Kit
- 2 ml cryotubes
- Pipettes
- -80°C freezer

Note: Conical tubes, cryotubes and Urine Conditioning Buffer will be provided by IARC.

3. Urine extraction

One sample of urine should be obtained before surgery (at least 40 mL).

4. Urine processing

Urine samples can stay at room temperature for a maximum of 2 hours before being processed in a laboratory or within 4 hours if kept refrigerated. If urine is not processed immediately, warm up the urine at 35-37 °C for 5 – 10 minutes. If it is and is visually cloudy, this may be caused by salt precipitation. If the urine does not turn clear after warming it up, it may be caused by bacterial contamination and should be discarded and be noted within the local inventory database.

The protocol below describes urine processing for storage of urine supernatant and urine pellet likely containing total cellular component. It is designed for the posterior isolation of DNA. All steps should be performed at room temperature (20 - 30 °C).

- i. Centrifuge from 20 ml to 40 ml urine (ideally 40 ml) in a 50 ml FALCON conical tube at 3,000 x g for 15 minutes.
- ii. Add 70 µl Urine Conditioning Buffer for every 1 ml of urine supernatant (e.g. add 2.8mL of Urine Conditioning Buffer to 40 ml urine) and vortex.
- iii. Centrifuge at 3,000 x g for 15 minutes. Without disturbing the pellet, carefully transfer urine supernatant to a new conical tube and keep it for next step. Using an appropriate disposable transfer pipette, aspirate off the pellet and transfer it to a cryovial with the label **urine-cell top**. Proceed to storage.

- iv. Aliquot recovered supernatant into 2-3 different labelled 2 ml cryovials with **urine-yellow top**. Discard the remaining supernatant and proceed to storage the aliquots.

NOTE 1: If for any reason there is less urine than expected aliquot less than required numbers.

NOTE 2: Record the number of aliquots.

Each tube will be labelled and coded with the subjects' full identification number ([Appendix 8](#)).

5. Storage

Store locally all obtained samples at -75 to -80°C. Follow same procedure as for blood samples.

NOTE: Optimal storage temperatures are -80°C or -190°C (liquid nitrogen). Storage in -20°C possible but is less favorable. If no other choice, store in -20°C and document the storage temperature.

IV. Collection and processing of tumor and peri-tumor or normal tissues

Where: Surgical blocks and pathology departments

Who: Operating theatre staff or research team technicians in conjunction with local pathologists

What: Pieces of tumor tissue and surrounding peri-tumor tissue

How: (i) Fresh tissue (cryopreserved or RNAlater® preserved), (ii) one extra formalin-fixed paraffin embedded (FFPE) piece, **or** (iii) one representative H&E stained (minimum required)

NOTE: 'Normal' tissues could be collected either from tissue surrounding a tumor in cancer patients or tissues in non-cancer patients and healthy subjects. Such tissues in the *mutographs* are collected from cancer patients and then called 'peri-tumor' in this SOP. All the instructions below regarding this type of collection are equally applied to 'normal' tissue collection in non-cancer patients or 'peri-tumor' tissue collection in cancer patients.

- The success of the *mutographs* study is dependent upon collection of fresh tumor tissue from each case.
- Tissue samples for all cancer sites will come predominantly from biopsy and/or surgical resection specimens.
- Confirmation of the adequacy of the materials for use in the *mutographs* study will be determined by a central pathology evaluation.

1. Tissue collection – general considerations (applicable to all nature of tissues and all organs)

Cellular and molecular integrity are most affected by pre-analytical elements such as hypoxia and ischemia, method of preservation, type of preservation, size of tissue, and storage conditions. The following factors must be considered to obtain and maintain tissue with suitable integrity for research application:

- Minimizing the hypoxia/ischemia time, as this initiates the cell death mechanisms and subsequent degradation process. Ideally, no more than 30 minutes should elapse between the time of surgical resection and time of freezing of a given sample. If, due to practical considerations, the elapsed time is greater, document the time lag between ligation of vessels and resection (time of **warm ischemia**) and the lag between resection and putting a collected piece of tissue in a container (time of **cold ischemia**). Such elapse time should be less than 1 min in endoscopic or fine needle biopsies.
 - Preservation of tissue as fresh frozen or use of agents or treatments to inactivate degrading enzymes for preserving nucleic acid integrity (such as RNAlater®).
 - Storage of frozen tissue and products at appropriate temperatures especially if storage is for longer periods of time.
 - The optimal storage temperatures are -80°C or -190° (liquid nitrogen). Storage in -20°C is possible but less favorable. If no other choice than -20°C, document the storage temperature and follow the manufacturer recommendations for RNAlater® preserved tissues (page 26).
 - Avoiding contamination with surrounding histological distinct tissue or co-processed samples.

NOTE: Recording the ischemia type applies to surgically resected pieces only.

Transport the tissue from the operating room to the pathology lab using a rapid specimen transport protocol. It is recommended to transport the tissue fresh, on ice and without any solution/fixative. **Particularly avoid putting the samples in normal saline or similar solutions. Direct contact between ice and tissues must be avoided.**

For all cancer types, the most appropriate time for collection of tumor tissues is **before any treatment, when it is the least disrupting for routine care**. Unless surgery is the first line treatment, as notably anticipated for kidney cancer, biospecimen should be collected at the time of biopsy. If surgery is subsequently performed, but still occurs before any further treatment, collection of tumor tissue should be repeated at the time of resection to maximize chances to obtain adequate tumor tissues; collection of peri-tumor tissue can also be repeated then.

The following specifications should be considered for collection of all type of tissues, regardless of nature (tumor tissue or peri-tumor/normal) or organ or type of procedure:

All kind of biological material should be considered as potentially infected (such as HIV, HBV) and universal safety precautions should be applied (gloves, protection glasses, needle, and blade disposal in specific safety containers).

For resection pieces

- Place the resection piece on a clean surface. Avoid contamination with other tissues and if possible, clean it with DNA away solution.
- The same attention should be given to the cutting instruments.
- **Record the time of warm (vascular clumping during the operation) and cold ischemia (from the resection of the organ to putting a piece in a collecting container).**
- Collection of tumor tissue for research is considered after collection of material needed for routine diagnostic procedures. The size of the remaining tumor tissues defines the number of pieces for research. The opinion of a pathologist may be sought in case the collection is performed by non-pathologists.
- Prepare the collection tubes and labels in advance.
- Always check the patient ID and the designated nature of the tissue that is going to be collected with the identification label.
- Collect one piece of tumor and one piece of peri-tumoral tissue (see below) as a minimum. Ideally, and if the availability of the material allows, collect at least two pieces of tissue per nature.
- Avoid grossly necrotic or ulcerated areas.
- Collect any grossly visible pathology, apart from tumor (such as polyps in a colectomy piece) in a tube separated from the tumor and peri-tumoral tissue. Identify the nature and document it.
- Pay attention to the ratio of the size of tissue/collection tube/volume of the preservative liquid. The maximum dimensions of pieces of tissues that allow an optimal penetration of preservation liquid of 5ml, such as RNA^{later}®, are 1x1x1 cm. (about 500 mg). The minimum dimensions are 0.5x0.5x0.5 cm. Note that the entire material needs to be fully submerged in the solution. For endoscopically collected mucosal biopsies, collect those with at least 3 mm in length and ≥ 1 mm in depth.
- If the local facilities allow, put only one piece of resected tissue in each cryovial. In any case, no more than two pieces of tissue per tube is recommended conditioned to respecting the size/weight and volume of preservative ratio (see above).
- For endoscopically collected mucosal biopsies a, no more than three biopsies per collection tube is recommended., if one biopsy per tube is not feasible.

- The ratio of preservative volume to tissue should be kept at about 10/1. Respect this ratio when one or more pieces are put in one tube.
- **Record the nature of each collected tissue through applying dedicated identification codes.**
- **Record the number of collected tissues (any nature) per tube.**
- **Record the number of tubes per nature of tissue.**
- Collection of peri-(non)tumoral tissues is strongly recommended and is expected to be done systematically, unless a special reason prevents it (for example too big tumor that does not leave enough peri-tumoral tissues, elongation of endoscopy time incompatible with the patient's status, etc.)
- If peri-tumoral tissues are not collected, explain why and document it.
- In addition to the above-mentioned specifications that apply to both tumor and peri-tumoral tissues, the following specifications should be considered when sampling peri-tumor tissues:
 - Avoid contamination of tumor with peri-tumor tissue.
 - Change the blade when switching to peri-tumor sampling. Use DNA away solutions to clean rigorously the cutting blade if changing it is not possible.
 - Collect the peri-tumor tissues at a distance where tumor is not grossly visible, and as far as possible.
 - **Record the distance between tumor and peri-tumoral tissue.**
 - Collect at least one, and preferably two, peri-tumor tissues, with the same size characterization that is explained for tumor tissues (see above).
 - Follow instructions of tissue preservation described in [section IV.6](#).

NOTE 1: *The use of fine needle aspiration (FNA) materials is not suitable for this research project, but core biopsies are acceptable.*

NOTE 2: *Collection and receiving the FFPE tissues, both from tumor and peri-tumor tissues, are of high interest and strongly recommended. This could happen through three scenarios:*

- a. One extra piece of tissue is collected in neutral buffered formalin 10% at the time of sampling and is processed by the recruiting center up to paraffin embedding, to be shipped with other collected biological material. This approach is the most preferable method and enables IARC to perform ancillary studies, such as IHC, when needed.
- b. The recruiting center agrees to ship one of the diagnostic FFPE blocks after completion of local routine diagnostic procedures.
- c. The recruiting center provides one H&E-stained slide from the most representative part of each pathology (the least preference) (see [Appendix 14](#) about quality control measures). This is the least favorable and the minimum requirement.

3. Organ specific considerations

A) Renal tissues

- Immediately transfer the resected piece, through partial or complete nephrectomy, to the pathology lab in fresh state, with no solution, and on a clean surface with ice but with no direct contact with ice.
- Perform grossing based on the standard instructions. Could be done in the operation theatre if a pathologist or fully trained assistant is available.

- Based on the opinion of the pathologist, take at least one piece of fresh tumor tissue, minimum dimensions of 0.5x0.5x0.5 cm. **Take the sections perpendicular to the direction of the mucosal folds (anatomical orientation of resection pieces).**
- Take a piece of peri-tumor tissue. If peri-tumor collection is not feasible, explain why, and record.
- Follow sample collection guidelines in .
- Deep freeze the collected tissues as explained above and in summary table.
- Record the anatomical location (topography) of sample collections.
- Process the remaining colectomy material to be fixed for the procedure of routine diagnosis.

B) Colorectal tissues

• Mucosal biopsies:

- Tumor: Ideally, at least 2 large biopsies, average size of 3x2x1 mm from tumor for the aim of research, in addition to the biopsies taken for diagnosis and immediately processed as per guidelines in section V.5-6.
- Peri-tumor: One biopsy of surrounding peri-tumor tissue should be taken and immediately processed as per guidelines in section V.5-6.
- Deep freeze the collected tissues as explained above and in summary table.
- Record the anatomical location (topography) of sample collection.
 - If peri-tumor collection is not feasible, explain why, and record.
- Anatomical orientation is necessary (see below)

• Colectomy (partial or total):

- Immediately transfer the resected piece, through segmental or total colectomy, to the pathology lab in fresh state, with no solution, and on a clean surface with ice but with no direct contact with ice.
- Perform grossing based on the standard instructions.
 - Could be done in the operation theatre if a pathologist or fully trained assistant is available.
- Based on the opinion of the pathologist, take at least one piece of fresh tumor tissue, minimum dimensions of 0.5x0.5x0.5 cm. **Take the sections perpendicular to the direction of the mucosal folds (anatomical orientation of resection pieces).**
- Take a piece of peri-tumor tissue.
 - If peri-tumor collection is not feasible, explain why, and record.
- Record the anatomical location (topography) of sample collection.
- Follow sample collection guidelines in .
- Deep freeze the collected tissues as explained above and in summary table.
- Process the remaining colectomy material to be fixed for the procedure of routine diagnosis.

C) Pancreatic tissues

• **Core needle biopsies through endoscopy procedures:** Core needle biopsies (ideally 2 per tumor) can be collected under CT or Ultrasound guidance and immediately processed as per guidelines in . One biopsy of surrounding peri-tumor tissues is of high interest.

• Pancreatectomy (Whipple or distal pancreatectomy):

- Immediately transfer the resected piece to the pathology lab in fresh state, with no solution, and on a clean surface with ice but with no direct contact with ice.

- Perform grossing based on the standard instructions.
- Based on the opinion of the pathologist, take at least one piece of fresh tumor tissue, minimum dimensions of 0.5x0.5x0.5 cm.
- Take a piece of peri-tumor tissue.
 - If peri-tumor collection is not feasible, explain why, and record.
- Record the anatomical locations (topography) of sample collection.
- Deep freeze the collected tissues as explained above and in summary table.
- Follow sample collection guidelines in .
- Process the remaining colectomy material to be fixed for the procedure of routine diagnosis.

D) Oesophageal tissues

- **Mucosal biopsies:** through upper GI endoscopy or staging laparoscopy as part of their routine clinical diagnostic procedures.
 - Tumor: Ideally, at least 2 large biopsies from tumor for the aim of research, in addition to the biopsies taken for diagnosis and immediately processed as per guidelines in .
 - Peri-tumor: One or more biopsies of surrounding peri-tumor tissue should be taken and immediately processed as per guidelines in .
 - Deep freeze the collected tissues as explained above and in summary table.
 - Anatomical orientation should be applied (see below).
- **Oesophagectomy:**
 - Immediately transfer the resected piece to the pathology lab in fresh state, with no solution, and on a clean surface with ice but with no direct contact with ice.
 - Perform grossing based on the standard instructions.
 - Based on the opinion of the pathologist, take at least one piece of fresh tumor tissue, minimum dimensions of 0.5x0.5x0.5 cm.
 - Take a piece of peri-tumor tissue.
 - If peri-tumor collection is not feasible, explain why, and record.
 - Record the anatomical locations (topography) of sample collection.
 - Follow sample collection guidelines in .
 - Deep freeze the collected tissues as explained above and in summary table.
 - Process the remaining colectomy material to be fixed for the procedure of routine diagnosis.

4. Anatomical orientation of endoscopically collected mucosal biopsies (applies only to non-tumor tissues)

Anatomical orientation of mucosal biopsies (see below) is mandatory. This procedure allows the preservation of the anatomic configuration of some specific mucosae (colon, esophagus, gall bladder, urinary bladder) that not only facilitates morphological evaluation but also enables the single structure dissection by laser capture microdissection (LCM) technology.

Equipment and Material

- Disposable syringe needle or tweezers with blunt tips (**left picture**).

- Avoid tweezers with cutting end.
- Filter papers such as nitrocellulose filter papers or Whatman filters, cut to rectangles of 1.5-2x1 cm.
- Collections tubes containing enough amount of RNAlater®

Procedure

Mucosal orientation should be done in less than 30 seconds to avoid tissue ischemia.

To avoid contamination of the biopsy with skin flora, change or clean your gloves before trying the orientation.

Orientation of mucosal biopsies need trained technicians by a pathologist or a pathologist. Follow the following steps to orient mucosal biopsies:

- After pulling out the biopsy forceps, while the forceps is kept open, by using a non-cutting side of a needle or a blunt-end tweezer, gently push the mucosal biopsy out of the forceps cup.
- Be careful not to smash or break the biopsy.
- Place the mucosal biopsy on a piece of previously prepared filter paper, **mucosal side up.**
- With the non-cutting edge of the needle or the tip of tweezer, gently flatten the biopsy and make it fully open and flat.
- Apply a very gentle pressure to stick it to the filter paper. Be careful not to smash the biopsy.

- Put the paper with the biopsy attached to it in the RNAlater® tube (containing the liquid).
- After overnight storage in the fridge, throw the liquid away (follow the precise manufacturer instructions). With the aid from a needle, gently separate the biopsy from the filter paper, put it back to the collecting tube (without liquid at this step) and store the tube in the -80 C freezer. ***Biopsy with filter paper could be frozen. If do not feel comfortable to separate the biopsy from the paper, freeze them together.***

If the size of biopsy is less than 3 mm in length or there is a concern that the tissue would be damaged during orientation, avoid this practice, and leave the mucosal biopsy in the tube without orientation. In this case no filter paper is required.

SUMMARY OF TISSUE COLLECTION and PRESERVATION

5. Processing of tissues for routine pathology examination

FFPE tissue blocks, and H&E-stained slides prepared from blocks, will be helpful for confirmation of diagnosis. Guidelines regarding the processing of tissues for routine pathology examination are provided in [Appendix 10](#). A pathology report abstract form will be filled in for each case ([Appendix 6](#)). Preparation of one extra FFPE block, from both tumor and peri-tumor tissues, for the purpose of research is highly desired. At least, one H&E-stained slide per patient, from a representative FFPE tumor block, should be sectioned for *mutographs*. This is highly recommended for all cancer types and the corresponding peri-tumor tissues. For shipment and scanning, refer to [Appendix 9](#).

Blocks and slides will be shipped to IARC. H&E-stained sections will be prepared from the FFPE block ([Appendix 14](#)). The in-house produced slides or externally received ones will be scanned to create high-resolution imaging for centralized pathology evaluation (see [Appendix 9](#) for shipment procedures). Alternatively, if the recruiting centres are equipped with a high-resolution scanner, slides can be scanned locally, and images will be shared with IARC for central storage and access.

6. Processing tissues for the purpose of research

NOTE: Routine diagnosis has the priority, and the purpose of research should not affect the microscopic diagnosis of the patient.

For resection samples obtained through surgical procedures, the pathologist will select representative parts of the tumor tissue for the purpose of the *mutographs* study. Processing follows snap-freezing techniques or preservation in RNAlater® solution, as described below. **Strive to preserve all surgically resected tissue samples within 30 minutes of excision from patient and preserve all biopsies immediately.** Resected tissues subject to delay of up to 2 hours should still be collected and the delay noted within the local inventory database. In any case, delays should be noted within the local inventory database:

- delay between clamping and preservation
- delay between excision and preservation

Cryopreservation

Preservation of tissue samples is by either cryopreservation or using RNAlater®. Direct cryopreservation or drained RNA later stored at -80°C is recommended, though any of the following options are acceptable:

Option A: Direct cryopreservation of tissue samples

1. Wrap the tissue samples (resection or biopsy) into an appropriate cryogenic tube, labelled with a freezer label containing a barcode and readable identifier (to make the sample identifier readable at institutions where there are no barcode readers and allow easier checking during manual inventory and sample processing). If barcoded labels cannot be used for practical reasons, use a waterproof pen able to withstand long-term storage at low temperature and handwrite the identifier.
2. Drop into the liquid nitrogen.

3. Storage: transfer the tissue samples to a pre-chilled storage container for transfer to either a locked -80°C freezer or liquid nitrogen storage facility in liquid or vapour phase. For storage longer than 5 years, liquid nitrogen is recommended. Enter storage location in the computerized database system.

4. Record sequential code, date, lag time from excision to freezing and the type of tissue (tumor or peri-tumor) in the inventory book or, if a barcode system is in use, scan into the Laboratory Information Management System and electronically record the above data.

Option B: Cryopreservation of OCT-embedded blocks

1. Place the optimal cutting temperature (OCT) pieces briefly on tissue paper and then embed tissue samples in OCT using the embedding chucks in the dry ice.

2. Once the OCT has set, wrap the embedded blocks in the OCT foil, labelled with a freezer label containing a barcode and readable identifier (to make the sample identifier readable at institutions where there are no barcode readers and allow easier checking during manual inventory and sample processing). If barcoded labels cannot be used for practical reasons, use a waterproof pen able to withstand long-term storage at low temperature and handwrite the identifier.

3. Drop into the liquid nitrogen.

4. Storage: transfer the OCT blocks to a pre-chilled storage container for transfer to either a locked -80°C freezer or liquid nitrogen storage facility in liquid or vapour phase. For storage longer than 5 years, liquid nitrogen is recommended. Enter storage location in the computerized database system.

5. Record sequential code, date, lag time from excision to freezing and the type of tissue (tumor or peri-tumor) in the inventory book or, if a barcode system is in use, scan into the Laboratory Information Management System and electronically record the above data.

Option C: Preservation in RNAlater® storage reagent

RNAlater® is a commercial aqueous, non-toxic tissue storage reagent that rapidly permeates tissues to stabilize and protect cellular RNA. RNAlater® eliminates the need to immediately process tissue samples or to freeze samples in liquid nitrogen for later processing.

1. For surgically resected materials, prepare the samples on a clean surface and using clean instruments (change or clean instruments between preparing tumor and peri-tumor tissue).

2. Cut tissue so that one edge has a dimension of maximum 0.5cm. For each patient, strive to cut 2-3 samples of tumor and 1-2 samples of peri-tumor tissue, ideally of 1cm x1 cm x 1cm. Submerge one sample (ideally) or at the maximum two samples (if necessary) of either tumor or peri-tumor tissues in one tube of 5ml RNAlater®. Note that the entire material needs to be fully submerged in the solution and weights no more than 500mg (maximum weight allowed in a 5ml RNAlater® tube for optimal preservation).

3. For biopsy materials, strive to take 2-3 biopsies of tumor and 1-2 biopsies of peri-tumor tissue, with average size of 3x2x1 mm. Put preferably one, and maximum three biopsies in each vial of RNAlater®.

4. Label RNA*later*[®] tubes with a freezer label containing a barcode and readable identifier (to make the sample identifier readable at institutions where there are no barcode readers and allow easier checking during manual inventory and sample processing). If barcoded labels cannot be used for practical reasons, use a waterproof pen able to withstand long-term storage at low temperature and handwrite the identifier.
5. Record sequential code, date, lag time from excision to submersion in RNA*later*[®] reagent, and the type of tissue (tumor or peri-tumor) in the inventory book or, if a barcode system is in use, scan into the Laboratory Information Management System and electronically record the above data.
6. Samples should be left overnight in a fridge (2°C to 8°C). The following morning, the tube can be moved to -20°C for longer term storage. If the tube is to be stored at -80°C, then the reagent **should first be drained away**. Enter storage location in the computerized database system.

NB: RNA*later*[®]-treated tissue samples can be stored at 25°C for one week, at 4°C for one month, and at -20°C or -80°C (without the reagent) for archiving.

V. Collection of initial pathology diagnosis data and review of local diagnoses

Where: Local pathology department, IARC and pathologist panel labs

Who: Local pathologist and/or research team, the panel of independent pathologists, and in-house pathologists and research team (IARC)?

What: Local pathology reports, H&E-stained slides from FFPE blocks at the time of the routine diagnosis, and corresponding high-resolution images

How: Pathology report abstract form, pathology review forms, and high-resolution scanner

1. Initial diagnosis

Pathological data, including stage of the disease, grade, and histological type and subtype will be obtained for each case using a standard abstract form ([Appendix 6](#)). This standard diagnosis and pathology form should be made available to the local pathologist ahead of any filling out procedure. Data abstract should be done by a qualified person with sufficient knowledge in cancer pathology.

Forms will be labelled with anonymized ID and data will be entered in the computerized system.

For microscopic evaluation of FFPE tissues see below, 'practice of central pathology at IARC'.

VI. Process and evaluation of tissue samples

Where: IARC and central database

Who: In-house pathologist, and the panel of independent pathologists for each organ

What: High-quality images created from scanning of H&E-stained slides from fresh frozen tissues

How: Standard protocol for processing tissues, scanning the slides and digital pathology for microscopic evaluation

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures for sectioning and staining of freshly preserved tissues. By examination of images from the H&E-stained slides of tumor tissue, the presence of the desired tumor and its histological type will be confirmed as well as the percentage of viable tumor cells and other cellular elements. Grading of the tumor or characterization of histological subtypes will be done when possible and applicable and considering the limitations of microscopy of fresh frozen tissue.

This procedure is intended to ensure that tissue samples preserved for the study are sectioned in a safe and consistent manner while eliminating the risks of contamination and loss of molecular and structural integrity. The SOP ensures that tissue sections are stained in a consistent manner and that the quantity of tissue prepared is sufficient for nucleic acid yields needed for the project.

2. Practice of central pathology at IARC

Central pathology at IARC practices digital pathology and is equipped to two digital slide scanners: 1) Medium-output (20 slides per run) from Glissando; 2) high-throughput (450 slides per run) from Leica (Aperio GT 450). This technology allows creation of high-resolution images and facilitates sharing the images with the external experts, according to the needs of each project, and obtain their opinion. Additionally, applying annotations for tumor enrichment approaches (see below) are easier by digital pathology. Each image size is expected to be around 800 Mb to 1.5 Gb. The platform is updated to the highest level of technology that enables performance of image analysis and to create, lead, or collaborate with experts in the field of neural network and artificial intelligence to augment the integration of morphology and molecular data. A trained research assistant regularly evaluates the quality of the images to assure the desired image resolution for microscopic examination and image analyses.

Both frozen and fixed tissues (FFPE block or H&E-stained image from a FFPE block) from tumor and peri-tumor are processed and examined microscopically by pathologists.

H&E-stained images from frozen tissues

Following processing of frozen tissues (see below), the high-quality-approved images will be evaluated by the central pathologist at IARC or the panel of expert pathologists, according to the needs of each project. The dedicated pathologist (s) perform an independent pathology evaluation while being blind to the diagnosis of the recruiting center, or the opinion of another pathologist. The items that are evaluated during microscopic examination of tumor tissues on the *mutographs* study are found in the [Appendix 11](#). All

pathology data are registered in the dedicated IARC pathology database, so called EASIER (rEdcap-based pAthology database for Iarc rEseaRch), that enables registering the pathology data of microscopic examination of all type of tissues. Dedicated organ-based templates have been created to facilitate such entry. EASIER has the capacity to be regularly updated and is under the regular maintenance by its developer and the central pathologist of IARC.

Whenever the diagnosis is not straight forward, the responsible pathologist has the possibility to ask for a second opinion. Such record will lead to a virtual meeting between panel of pathologists to discuss the case and to reach to a final agreed diagnosis. If not, a third opinion or an expert opinion out of the panel will be obtained. In addition, a 20% random selection of cases will undergo a second independent evaluation. Specific access codes will be created to make sure that the latter is independent and conducted blind to the initial diagnosis.

EASIER enables registering the pathology data of microscopic examination of peri-tumor tissues. Dedicated organ-based templates have been created to facilitate such entry.

H&E-stained images from formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissues

Such images are created either by simultaneous receive of a FFPE block that is processed at IARC to obtain an image or by scanning the H&E-stained slides from the recruiting center. The created images become available to the responsible pathologist at the time of reporting the frozen tissues to provide more diagnostic precision if necessary. Externally prepared H&E-stained slides from FFPE blocks go through quality control evaluation by a trained research assistant and based on the shared SOP ([Appendix 14](#)) that specifies the minimum quality measures of H&E-stained slides from FFPE tissues to assure the quality of images. If reversible technical quality issues are detected (such as air under the coverslip, pen marking over the slide, etc.), the dedicated research assistant tries improving the quality. If the quality issue is strong and irreversible, the slide will not be scanned.

3. Sectioning the frozen tissue

Frozen tumor tissues are subjected to be used for DNA extraction and molecular studies. Following confirmation of diagnosis of the eligible tumor type and estimation of enough viable tumor cells, thick sections are prepared for DNA extraction followed by additional H&E-stained slides/images in the middle and at the end for confirmation of the existence of at least 50% of viable tumor cells. Overall, the following procedure is followed:

- One 3-5 μ m and H&E-stained slide at the beginning for microscopic examination, confirmation of diagnosis and estimation of the percentage of viable tumor cells.
- 10-20 thick sections (10 μ m) in one cryovials for DNA extraction.
- The exact number of sections will be determined based on the surface size of the examined section.
- One 3-5 μ m and H&E-stained slide at the middle to confirm the enough percentage of viable tumor cells.
- Second tube of 10-20 thick sections (10 μ m) for DNA extraction.
- One 3-5 μ m and H&-stained slide at the end containing at least two sections to confirm the enough percentage of viable tumor cells.

- In case of small tumor size or low percentage of isolated tumor cells, pathologist decides and asks for one of the tumor enrichment methods, as below:
 - Macrodissection of the unwanted area that is annotated by the pathologist, in the pathology lab and by using a surgical scalpel.
 - Collection of the area of interest, annotated by pathologist, by laser capture microdissection (LCM). The collected pieces will be processed accordingly for manual DNA extraction ([chapter X](#)).
 - In case of surface size $\leq 1\text{mm}^2$, measured by pathologist during examination, the entire piece is directly used for DNA extraction [chapter X](#).

Figure 2. Schematic view of frozen tissue sections preparation.

4. Sectioning of frozen tissue

This protocol applies to both snap-frozen tissue and samples preserved in RNA/ater®. Tissue samples will be embedded in OCT at the time of section preparation, if not done before storage.

Sectioning

1. The frozen tissue cryomolds are transferred to the cryotome on dry ice.
2. For tissue stored at -80°C , remove from freezer and equilibrate at -20°C for 15 minutes (this may prevent cracking of the block when sectioning).
3. Section tissue at a range of $3\text{--}5\ \mu\text{m}$ and place on positively charged slides.
4. Allow sections to air dry on bench for a few minutes before fixing (this helps sections adhere to slide).
5. For nucleic acid extraction, allow the tissue $20\ \mu\text{m}$ sections to roll naturally and place them into pre-labelled, pre-cooled Eppendorf tubes.
6. Samples can be stored at -80°C or alternatively the appropriate extraction buffer can be added immediately and stored at -80°C

Fixation

1. After sections have dried on the slide, fix with Formaldehyde 4% (Polysciences Cat18814).

2. Allow slides to fix for 15 minutes at room temperature.
3. Rinse slides three times in PBS for 5 minutes each.

H&E staining

1. Haematoxylin (hemalun de Masson modifie) 5 minutes.
2. Erythrosine 0.1% 3 minutes.
3. Dehydrate slides 95% ethanol, absolute ethanol, xylene: 5 min in each solution.

VII. Sample shipping and transportation

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

During the operation of the tissue biobank, samples will require shipping to different locations. Human Biological Materials (HBMs) are a precious and delicate resource. During the shipping process, care should be taken to protect and maintain sample integrity.

This standard operating procedure (SOP) outlines processes for shipping samples nationally and internationally between study partners. The SOP specifies considerations that should be followed to ensure appropriate packaging and shipping of the samples.

Collection centres must only ship samples to researchers or to a designated third-party laboratory involved in the study. An established and tested shipping procedure is essential, as inadequate shipping procedures may lead to the loss of the samples, additional costs for repeat shipments.

- The safe and legal transport of patient specimens is based on the following mandated activities:
- Classification and naming of the material to be shipped.
- Selection of packaging that will contain the contents if the package is damaged.
- Packing the shipment correctly.
- Placing appropriate markings and labels onto the outer package.
- Documenting relevant aspects of each package and its contents.
- Training individuals about the requirements for appropriate packaging and shipping of specimens.

2. Biological material transfer agreement

Before samples are shipped between various locations, material transfer agreement (MTA) will be signed between institutes as appropriate. IARC templates will be provided.

3. Appropriate packaging and shipping conditions

1. Packaging must be appropriate for the transportation of perishable goods. Contents of the package may be categorized as being dangerous or biohazardous and so packaging must conform to transportation regulations (www.iata.org) regarding appropriate labelling and packaging.

2. IATA has defined a "patient specimen" as material collected directly from human or animals for diagnostic, treatment, prevention, investigational or research purposes. Patient specimens have to be categorized as Category A, Category B or Exempt Specimens. Specific description of all categories is available in [Appendix 9](#). Only Category B and Exempt Specimens apply to the *mutographs* study.

3. The samples must be shipped in a leakproof primary container, a leakproof secondary container, absorbent material between the two and an outer packaging.

4. Ship all frozen products in cryovials and frozen sections on dry ice.

Dry ice is classified as a dangerous substance and needs to be sent in a double insulated shipper (styrofoam container in fitted cardboard box). Dry ice must NEVER be placed into a tightly sealed container (explosion hazard); the packaging must allow the release of CO₂.

5. Ship paraffin blocks and slides with paraffin sections at room temperature.

6. To prevent damage during shipping and ensure leakproof conditions, cryovials must be inserted in cardboard or plastic vial shippers. Glass slides must be inserted in slide shipping cassettes to prevent breakage and damage.

7. The quantity of samples to be shipped will affect the size of the packaging. Add sufficient refrigerant to maintain desired temperature throughout the shipping cycle. Use sufficient dry ice to ensure that the sample will remain frozen even if delayed in transit for 48-72 hours.

8. Tape and seal the packaging securely to prevent condensation of refrigerant and provide additional security for the contents.

9. Affix appropriate labels required to comply with shipping regulations and to ensure timely and proper shipping protocol (ie, dry ice declaration sticker, "Keep Frozen" sticker, etc.)

10. Before use, validate packaging to make sure it is able to maintain appropriate conditions of temperature, humidity, light sensitivity, structural quality and spill containment if relevant.

4. Appropriate supporting documentation

1. Contact the courier to establish what supporting documentation is needed to ship the sample to the specified destination. For international shipments, research any new regulations that may have been adopted or special permits that are needed for that destination.

2. Complete shippers Waybill and ProForma Invoice (to provide contact information and to declare nature of contents to customs and regulatory agencies).

3. Dry ice is a Class 9 dangerous good and requires completion of a shipper's declaration.

5. Appropriate courier

1. Identify and build a relationship with a courier that can consistently deliver frozen shipments within 24 hours.
2. To ensure package is traceable use established couriers.
3. Assess and choose couriers for following characteristics:
 - Reliability.
 - Experience with and ability to routinely ship biologics and HBMs to national and international destinations.
 - Ability to provide online tracking of shipments.
 - Knowledge about relevant transportation regulations and permits.
 - Existence of established, standardized paperwork accompanying shipments.
 - Efficient customer service ensuring that unforeseen delays and deviations are tracked and communicated to relevant personnel.
 - Customer service agents capable of troubleshooting and expediting shipments in accordance with temperature and time sensitivity of the samples.
 - Willingness to "top-up" dry ice in the package in the event of a delay in transit.

6. Shipping log

1. Maintain a shipping log to record receipt and dissemination of shipments.
2. Track the following items:
 - Invoice number
 - Waybill number for tracking package
 - Recipient/Source
 - Date received or shipped
 - Courier name and contact information
 - Sample description
 - Quantity shipped
 - Researchers name
 - Study Name
 - Confirmation of delivery.

7. Shipping procedure

1. The day before the shipment is to go out, verify that there is an adequate stock of dry ice available.
2. Before scheduling a pick-up, assemble packaging material, refrigerants, and samples to be shipped, accompanying documentation, shipping documentation and permits.
3. Contact shipper to schedule package pick-up.

4. Verify that all shipping information, contacts and required documents are accurate and complete.
5. It is optimal to specify to whose attention the shipment is being delivered. This measure should prevent the shipment from arriving and being held in the receiving department for too long.
6. Retrieve samples from storage and keep frozen on dry ice until packaged.
7. Use appropriate safety procedures when handling dry ice or when retrieving samples from liquid nitrogen containers.
8. Document sample retrieval in repository database and complete shipping log according to established procedure.
9. Verify that samples match researcher's request.
10. Package samples as is appropriate.
11. Contact (call or e-mail) consignee to provide them with Waybill number and inform them that package has been shipped. Give them an estimated delivery time so that they can anticipate arrival of the samples.
12. Track delivery using the online tracking capability of the courier to monitor shipment and expedite sample if delayed by customs or regulatory agencies.
13. Timing of shipping (to prevent delays in-transit):
 - Schedule pick-up early in the day so that the package goes out on the earliest flight available.
 - Schedule pick-up for early in the week (Monday or Tuesday) to prevent delays in shipment or delivery due to the week-end schedules;
 - Do not ship just before a holiday long week-end as it usually translates into delays in transit;
 - Be aware of public holidays in the province or country of destination to plan for optimal shipping dates.

8. Guidelines for shipment of samples to IARC

Specific guidelines are available in [Appendix 9](#).

9. Guidelines for shipment of samples to the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute

Specific guidelines are available in [Appendix 15](#). A sample manifest will accompany any shipment and provide the following minimal information: type of materials, species, volume supplied, sample ID, sex, age at diagnosis, tissue type and specimen type. Repeated samples will be flagged, if applicable ([Appendix 15](#)).

VIII. DNA purification from blood samples

Where: IARC

Who: IARC staff

What: germline DNA

How: Automated protocol on Autopure (Qiagen)

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

When extracting and storing DNA from blood samples all efforts should be made to avoid contamination, prevent degradation and preserve molecular integrity. The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures used at IARC. Should local extraction of DNA from blood samples be applicable, it should first be discussed with IARC staff to ensure standardization of extraction processes.

This procedure is intended to ensure that DNA is extracted from blood samples in a safe and consistent manner while eliminating the risks of contamination and loss of molecular and structural integrity. Consistency in procedure is important for obtaining comparable and reliable test results.

2. Protocol of DNA purification from blood samples (Qiagen Autopure protocol)

2.1. All samples are registered in the database. Edition of a new unique barcode specific for each sample. All samples are labelled with a sampling ID (study name and number associated to the sample) and a barcode readable by operator with and without use of bar code reader. The volume of blood used to isolate the buffy-coat is also registered.

2.2. All blood samples are extracted on the Autopure (Qiagen) using an automated protocol based on the salting-out method. Different protocols are usable for each type of biological material (frozen buffy-coat, frozen whole blood...) depending on the type and quality of biological material. Three versions of each protocol are available depending on the initial blood sample volume collected (1-5ml, 4-7ml and 5.1-10ml blood). Frozen buffy-coats stored at -80°C are extracted using the protocol called "Fresh buffy Coats Increased Spin". Glycogen solution (Qiagen) is also used to improve the DNA precipitation (66.5 µl for the 1-5ml protocol, 93.1 µl for the 4-7ml protocol and 133µl for the 5.1-10ml protocol).

2.3. DNA samples are hydrated using 100-200 µl of DNA Hydration Solution (Qiagen). DNAs are incubated twice at 65°C for 1h and rotated at room temperature for 7 days.

3. DNA quantification

Quantifications are done using Quant-iT™ Picogreen® dsDNA quantification reagent (Invitrogen). Two to four measures are performed on a single DNA to ensure accuracy.

4. DNA quality control

Quality controls beyond spectrophotometric overview are performed at the Sanger Institute, following recommendations of providers of DNA library preparation kits. Sex matching check between germline and tumor DNA of each individual is also systematically performed using an in-house SNPs set.

5. Storage

5.1. Two aliquots of stock DNAs are prepared if the volume of DNA is higher than 1ml to allow a long-term storage in two different freezers.

5.2. Aliquots are prepared for the genome analysis.

5.3. Stock DNAs are stored at -80°C.

IX. Cellular content enrichment

Where: IARC pathology lab and Centre Leon Berard, Lyon

Who: Dedicated pathologist; trained assistant

What: Tumor or any other tissue to enrich cellularity of interest

How: Macrodissection or Laser Capture Microdissection (LCM)

Enrichment of the cell of interest is a method to enrich the purity of tumor cells or other cellular elements, when needed. The choice between available possibilities is provided by a pathologist after microscopic evaluation of the tissue and providing an initial estimate of the percentage of the area or the cells of interest. This could be applied to augment the purity of tumor cells or any other cell of interest.

1. Macrodissection

This enrichment method is applied when the percentage of viable cells of interest, for example tumor cells, in the examined piece of tissue is not enough to extract pure DNA at the quantity that is requested for a specific technical platform, such as sequencing. In the *mutographs*, the minimum percentage of viable tumor cells to make a tissue eligible for whole genome sequencing is 50%. Upon microscopic examination, the responsible pathologist defines if the enrichment is technically feasible by gross cutting of the 'unwanted' area, such as tumor necrosis or non-tumor cells that are around each tumor. In this situation, the area of interest (AOI) is annotated by using specific tools provided by image viewer programs. Technical research cuts the unwanted area by following the annotations, creates a new OCT-block of the AOI, prepares sections and new images of the newly created block. The same pathologist evaluates the newly created images and if the enrichment is successful, confirms the inclusion of the case. In case of unsuccessful technical intervention, the pathologist decides about possibility of other approaches, such as LCM (see below), or performance of another macrodissection, or eventually, excluding the case. All the new images and the corresponding reports are accordingly registered in EASIER database.

2. Laser Capture Microdissection (LCM)

This technology is used when the AOI (tumor cells in the *mutographs*, applicable to any AOI based on the research strategy) is too small to be treated and collected macroscopically. This technology acts through a motorized microscope equipped to laser beams at the wavelength of infrared or ultraviolet, based on the technology, to cut the annotated AOI.

During microscopic examination of the first image and based on the instructions of pathologist, this approach is applied to collect isolated tumor cells (or any other cell of interest) by avoiding confounding unwanted cells to provide high purity material. The technology is time consuming but saves extremely low-cellular tumor tissues or those that have sparse cells of interest by collecting very small nests of cells or even single cells. Fresh (or fixed) sections of 10 um thickness are prepared on the day of procedure and will be stained by crystal violet. A pathologist or a trained assistant detects the annotated AOI and is cut by laser beam. The obtained material is directly collected in the specific extraction tubes compatible with direct DNA extraction. The tubes are stored in -80° C until the extraction of nucleic acids.

X. DNA purification from tumor tissue samples

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

When extracting and storing nucleic acids from tumor tissue samples all efforts should be made to avoid contamination, prevent degradation, and preserve molecular integrity. The purpose of this chapter is to outline standardized procedures to follow when extracting nucleic acids from frozen tissue samples.

This procedure is intended to ensure that nucleic acids are extracted from frozen tissue samples in a safe and consistent manner while eliminating the risks of contamination and loss of molecular and structural integrity. Consistency in procedure is important for obtaining comparable and reliable test results.

2. Protocol of DNA purification from fresh frozen tissues (QIAGEN QIASymphony DSP protocol)

Remarks:

- Avoid repeated freezing and thawing of stored samples, since this leads to reduced DNA size.
- Use cryovials containing 20 sections (10µm each) of tissue preserved in RNAlater® solution (at -20°C with RNAlater® solution or at -80°C without RNAlater® solution) or snap-frozen tissue stored at -80°C, OCT-embedded.

2.1. All samples are registered in the database. Edition of a new unique barcode specific for each sample. All barcodes are unique and specific for each sample and each biological material. All samples are labelled with a sampling ID (cohort name and number associated to the sampling) and a barcode readable by operator with and without use of barcode reader. The number of tissue sections is also registered.

2.2. **Wash tissue sections to remove OCT:** Add 1ml of PBS on tissue sections in storage tubes, transfer in 15ml tubes and complete with PBS up to a total volume of 10ml. Centrifuge at 2000 rpm for 5min and remove the supernatant. Repeat this wash with 5ml of PBS, centrifuge again for 5 min at 2000 rpm and remove the supernatant.

2.3. All tissue samples are extracted on the QIASymphony (Qiagen) using a fully automated protocol based on magnetic-particle technology. The purification procedure is designed to enable purification of high-quality nucleic acids, free of proteins, nucleases and other impurities, and comprises 4 steps: lyse, bind, wash and elute. It is performed using QIASymphony DNA Mini Kit with the Tissue_HC DSP protocol according to the manufacturer's instructions. Eluted DNA is ready to be stored at -20°C until use.

3. Protocol of DNA purification from microdissected materials

For a proportion of the tumor samples, the amount of tissue materials will be limited (biopsies, macro or microdissected materials). In such cases, DNA purification will be using the *QIASymphony DSP DNA Mini Kit* with the *Tissue_LC_DSP* protocol.

4. DNA quantification

Quantifications are done using Quant-iT™ Picogreen® dsDNA quantification reagent (Invitrogen). Two to four measures are performed on a single DNA to ensure accuracy.

5. DNA quality control

Quality controls beyond spectrophotometric overview are performed at the Sanger Institute, following recommendations of providers of DNA library preparation kits. Sex matching check between germline and tumor DNA of each individual is also systematically performed using an in-house SNPs set.

6. Storage

6.1. Two aliquots of stock DNAs are prepared if the volume of DNA is higher than 1ml to allow a long-term storage in two different freezers.

6.2. DNA aliquots are prepared and transferred to the lab in charge of the genetic study.

6.3. Stock DNAs are stored at -80°C.

7. Use of previously extracted DNA

It may happen that the DNA from fresh tissues of an eligible case is directly available (e.g., already extracted for the purpose of another project). Providing that the extraction protocol is validated by IARC and that the DNA materials passes quantity and quality controls detailed in this chapter, the DNA may be used for sequencing. Please contact IARC staff to discuss applicability.

XI. Compiling “dry” data (clinical, demographical, lifestyle, outcome, pathological data) and tracking biosamples and aliquots

Where: IARC, recruiting centres, sequencing laboratory

Who: Research teams

What: Central database

How: Computerized sample management systems

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

The purpose of this Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) is to outline general procedures that are used to ensure that tracking is maintained with essential standards to prevent loss of samples due to inadequate identifying information and to adequately link patient and sample information.

All the samples related data as well as clinical, demographical, lifestyle, outcome and pathological data will be centralized in a common database. This database will be accessible online through a web-based interface and will contain anonymised information about patients and samples. This web-based tool will allow upload, management and retrieval of research subject data and sample information (quality, quantity and location). The pre – selection of samples and data quality check is described below.

2. Patient information

Data quality checking will be performed on the obtained information. Data consistency (i.e., birth data, smoking status, etc.) and missing data will be systematically analysed at IARC.

3. List of biological samples involved

- From blood:

- Buffy coat
- DNA
- Plasma
- RBC

- From all organ sites:

- Tumor tissue specimen
- Peri-tumor tissue specimen
- Paraffin block from FFPE tissue
- H&E slides from FFPE tumor tissue
- H&E slides from frozen tumor tissue
- DNA from tumor tissue

4. Keeping track of biological samples at each storage location

A tracking and inventory should be in place to ensure that a sample can be located at any time during collection, processing, storage, and distribution for effective project management and to comply with regulations. It should also be designed to ensure that the sample environment is kept as stable as possible during processing, storage, sorting and shipping.

1. Assign a unique identifier such as a tracking number or bar-code to each sample at the time of collection
2. Link the same identifier to all associated clinical and scientific data for the sample.
3. Update the inventory or tracking system to reject any movement or change in the sample or data within or outside the repository.
4. Ensure that the inventory and tracking system is capable of generating a full audit trail of changes made to the database or system,
5. Control access to the computerized inventory very tightly. Define what tasks a specific tumor bank employee may perform on the system (e.g., entering data or determining specimen availability).
6. Generate a unique identifier (address) for each freezer, refrigerator, or storage cabinet. Establish numbering for shelves, racks, boxes as well as each location within the storage receptacle.
7. Use the inventory system to track sample type, date of collection, volume and size of aliquots, history of sample movement, method and time of sample processing, shipment and thaws and deviations from regular storage conditions if relevant.

For the *mutographs* study, a computerized, unique, reliable and secured system needs to be maintained in all locations that will store biospecimens (IARC, the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute, as well as local centres) to keep track of all samples, their locations within the storage facilities, and the history of their movements and transformations. The systems may lay on pre-existing laboratory information management systems, provided they cover the following:

- Unique biospecimen ID that can be linked to a patient ID
- Location of each sample
- History of movements
- History of transformations
- In case of transformation, duration of the process
- Quantity of each sample: volume and concentration when appropriate
- Any derived product is linked to the original repository sample

Example of system used at IARC

IARC uses a system called "SAMI" for biosample tracking (Voegele *et al.* 2010). The system is accessible via login from any computer connected to the internal network. Rights in writing or reading data depend on user who logs in: only allowed users have permission to write in data. Data are imported through forms or Excel files and the retrieval of information is enabled through multi-criteria queries that can generate different types of reports including tables, Excel files, trees, pictures and graphs. All the sample movements, both internal and external, are recorded in the database allowing quick and straightforward localization of samples and their aliquots.

5. Keeping track of all biological samples in a unique central database

Twice a month (before the 15th and the 31st), each laboratory involved in sample storage and/or transformation will upload to the central database an update of the status of each sample that has been through the local repository, even though the sample is no longer there. "Dry" data will be updated in a similar manner.

The lists of variables needed for the upload are available in [Appendix 12](#); as much as possible, this should be a direct output of the local databases. Alternatively, data could be entered directly into the central *mutographs* database. Data from the pathology review will be entered directly into the database.

XII. Overall workflow for case selection

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

Effectively, all the stages of sample and data collection and processing need an effective logging/tracking system in place so that at any time it is easy to see which samples have been requested and at what level and where they currently are in the overall process. This will allow monitoring of the process and receiving updates of what is happening but also for legal reasons as tissue has to be tracked effectively according to various different countries' requirements. Moreover, all the stages of sample and data collection and processing require careful review as all samples must meet strict study inclusion criteria. This chapter describes the workflow for case selection.

2. Pre-selection of cases

In the *mutographs* project, several criteria should be followed for case inclusion, including:

- I. Patient-matched blood samples, representative for the germline genome, are mandatory to discern "somatic" from "inherited" mutations.
- II. Questionnaire information representing a minimum set of risk factor information ([Appendix 12](#)).
- III. Tumor samples should be untreated malignancies, i.e., in general primary and not relapsed, representing one of the selected histological type/subtypes
- IV. Histological examination will have to be documented and respective optical images must be stored and be available to those studying the given tumor entity.
- V. The following samples should be available for each case:
 - Blood sample
 - Tumor tissue
 - H&E-stained slides from FFPE tumor block (the minimum requirement for FFPE tissue)
 - Good quality clinical data
- VI. The minimum set of clinical variables that must be collected for each tumor sample are:
 - General data (Date of Birth (DOB), age, gender, date of diagnosis, presence of metastases, etc.).
 - Diagnostic data (histological and other data).
- VII. Acquisition of follow-up information is highly recommended for subsequent clinical correlations:
 - Therapies after removal of malignant cells.
 - Response to therapy (event-free survival (EFS), complete remission (CR), overall survival (OS), definition of end points of trials).

The schematic diagram representing the sequence of events during the selection is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Selection of cases eligible for the *mutographs* study.

Left panel shows the procedures performed; right panel indicates reasons for potential exclusion. App. – Annex_; * cases can re-enter the process if duplicate sample is available.

3. Notifications

SIMS will be set up to notify relevant persons (e.g., coordinator, pathologists, ...) when new data has been uploaded (e.g., pathology review, scanned images, ...)

XIII. Biobank quality control and assurance

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

Generating collections of high-quality tumor samples and clinical data is likely to be a major challenge of the *mutographs* study. Therefore, the *mutographs* concept is based on the assumption that the diagnosis, the collection of samples, clinical and lifestyle data and their processing in collaborating centres is performed in a homogenous manner (using the same methodology). The Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) manual was developed specifically for the *mutographs* study that states policies and describes all procedures in detail.

Quality assurance procedures apply to the verification of:

- The homogeneity of methodologies used in the centres for data collection, sample processing and storage.
- The coherence of *mutographs* electronic data with paper and source data and medical records.

In addition, quality control is fundamental to the successful operation of the biobank offering tissue specimens for research purposes. Testing procedures should be in place to monitor and assess the quality and integrity of the sections released for prospective research studies.

2. Clinical data

The continuous challenge in managing the quality of clinical data is to monitor data collection procedures and data management practices at every level of the study. This includes:

- ensuring that data generated during the study reflect what is specified in the protocol.
- comparing data in the Central Database and data collected in source documents for accuracy.
- ensuring that the data analysed are the data recorded in the *mutographs* database.

During the data management process, the data quality checking is performed to verify the accuracy of the initial data entry by an independent entry of the same data and a subsequent comparison of both sets of data for non-agreement. The accuracy of the data is checked with a pre-programmed logic check program enclosed into the *mutographs* central database and a subsequent manual review by a data manager.

- Quality management of clinical data ensures:
 - compliance with the protocol.
 - enables systemic problems to be resolved before the end of the study.
 - helps reduce data queries.
 - data integrity throughout the study's course and that the data collected are the data required by the protocol.
 - accuracy and consistency of data from entry into the beginning of the *mutographs* study to final datasets reported in the central database.

3. Histopathological data

The basis of the control of quality of the pathological review and analysis between different centres is the use of shared protocols for sampling, processing and analysis of specimens as described in the previous chapters. Although local hospital standards for technical procedures for fixation, embedding, sectioning and staining will be used, they will be similar and should not interfere with the experimental protocols.

Pathological variables will be scored according to preliminarily defined sets of values. Some samples will be reviewed by two or more reference pathologists. This assessment will need to be performed on stained slides of the very same tissue piece from which DNA will be purified. Tumor types are defined using the existing international standards of the ICDO-3 (First revision 2011). Histological examination must be documented, and respective optical images must be stored and made available. The recommendations of ICGC about using virtual slides are used in the study.

4. Laboratory data

Quality Control is an important part of every laboratory test. Appropriate Quality Control practices maximize the accuracy of results reported and provide early information of problems.

Tumor-matched blood samples will be used in the study, which are representative for the germline genome and essential to discern "somatic" from "inherited" mutations. It is envisioned that tumor sample inclusion criteria will require over 50% of each sample to be composed of viable-appearing tumor cells on histological assessment.

The quality of the isolated nucleic acids is controlled by standardized procedures (see sections IX and XI). For example, assessing the purity and the quality of extracted DNA is fundamental. The gold standard methods used in this field are the Nanodrop spectrophotometer, fluorometric measurement of concentration and electrophoresis on agarose gel. Nanodrop calculates the 260/280 and 260/230 absorbance ratio. First ratio gives an estimation of protein contamination, and it must be between 1.8 and 2. The second one reflects carbohydrates contamination, and it must be greater than 1.5. Electrophoresis allows checking the integrity of DNA. Fluorimetry allows an accurate measure of double-stranded DNA concentration. Low quantity and/or low-quality DNA sample will be excluded.

XIV. Whole genome sequencing of tumour and germline DNA, bioinformatics analysis and subsequent posting of data

1. Purpose and scope of the procedure

DNA samples from more than 6000 individuals with cancers of the colorectum, pancreas, kidney, oesophagus, gall bladder and urothelial carcinoma from regions of high or low cancer incidence will be sequenced to find mutational signatures with differing mutation burdens and to correlate these differences with epidemiological risk factors such as obesity and environmental exposures.

2. Whole genome sequencing of tumour and germline DNA

Whole genome libraries will be prepared using 500ng of genomic DNA. Libraries will be constructed from the tumour and corresponding peri-tumour sample. The resulting libraries will be QC'd and sequenced on the Illumina platform to a 40X and 20X depth respectively.

3. Bioinformatics analysis

The primary sequence data from cancer and normal samples will be entered into the WTSI variant calling pipelines, which will identify somatic mutation, followed by implementation of non-negative matrix factorisation (NNMF) to extract mutational signatures. The studies will address base substitution, genome rearrangement and copy number signatures to improve precision of signature profiles, estimation of signature contributions, co-analysis of all mutation types, integration of further mutational characteristics, and incorporation of genome landscape features such as across-genome variation in mutation rates.

4. Data sharing

Data generated at different stages of data processing will be organized and released using procedures and infrastructure that are routinely employed at the Sanger Institute for release of cancer genome data and that are being developed in a bespoke manner for mutational signature studies.

Primary next generation DNA sequence data, in the form of BAM or CRAM files, which has undergone basic quality control by the core pipelines at Sanger, will be automatically released within two months of being generated to the European Genome-phenome Archive.

To use the data cancer researchers will have to request access online, state the purpose of their data use and agree not to identify the individuals involved. The request is scrutinised by a responsible person and, if agreed, the relevant processes enabled for download.

The variant calls will be released into the COSMIC database together with clinical data (<http://cancer.sanger.ac.uk/cosmic>).

The mutational signatures and associated analyses for each sample will be released into the new database / portal currently being configured by the COMSIG collaboration. This database will hold naturally occurring mutational signatures from cancers and/or normal cells and signatures generated from experimental systems. This portal will be constituted within and linked to the COSMIC family of databases and websites.

The Mutographs study is also part of the ICGC-ARGO initiative, second phase of the International Cancer Genome Consortium project, that will link omics data together with treatment and outcome information. In this context, data will be shared as per ICGC procedures and policies (<https://icgc-argo.org/>).

Appendices

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[Appendix 15. Sanger Institute's shipment procedures](#)

Appendix 1. List of partners

Continent	Recruitment site: Country	Local PI: Contact Points	Local PI: Affiliation	Local PI: City	Local PI: Country
Africa	Kenya	Diana Menya	Moi University	Eldoret	Kenya
Africa	Kenya	Francis Makokha	Mount Kenya University	Thika	Kenya
Africa	South Africa	Christopher Mathew	University of Witwatersrand - Sydney Brenner Institute	Johannesburg	South Africa
Africa	South Africa	Iqbal Parker	University of Cape Town	Cape Town	South Africa
Africa	South Africa	Paul Ruff	Wits Health Consortium (Pty) Limited ("WHC") University of the Witwatersrand	Johannesburg	South Africa
Africa	Tanzania	Blandina Theophil Mmbaga	Kilimanjaro Clinical Research Institute (KCRI)	Moshi	Tanzania
Africa	Uganda	Jackson Orem	Uganda Cancer Institute	Kampala	Uganda
Africa	Uganda	Rob Newton	MRC/UVRI Uganda Research Unit on AIDS	Entebbe	Uganda
Asia	China	Alisa Goldstein Phil Taylor Stephen Chanock	NCI		USA
Asia	Iran	Reza Malekzadeh Ahmadreza Niavarani Ramin Shakeri	Teheran University Medical School	Teheran	Iran
Asia	India	Rajesh Dikshit	Tata Memorial Centre	Mumbai	India
Asia	Japan	Tatsuhiro Shibata	National Cancer Center	Tokyo	Japan

Asia	Thailand	Suleeporn Sangrajrang	National Cancer Institute	Bangkok	Thailand
Asia	Thailand	Taned Chitapanarux	Chiang Mai University	Chiang Mai	Thailand
Asia	Thailand	Surasak Sangkhathat	Prince Songkla of Songkla University	Songkhla	Thailand
Asia	Pakistan	Amjad Khan	Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences	Jamshoro	Pakistan
Europe	Czech Republic	Ivana Holcatova	Charles University in Prague	Prague	Czech Republic
Europe	Lithuania	Sonata Jarmalaite; Feliksas Jankevicius	National Cancer Institute	Vilnius	Lithuania
Europe	Poland	Beata Swiatkowska	Nofer Institute of Occupational Medicine	Lodz	Poland
Europe	Poland	Jolanta Lissowska	Maria Sklodowska-Curie Memorial Institute of Oncology	Warsaw	Poland
Europe	Russian Federation	David Zaridze	N.N. Blokhin Cancer Research Center	Moscow	Russian Federation
Europe	Serbia	Miodrag Ognjanovic	International Organization for Cancer Prevention and Research	Belgrade	Serbia
Europe	United Kingdom	Rebecca Fitzgerald	University of Cambridge	Cambridge	United Kingdom
Europe	United Kingdom	Roz Banks; Naveen Vasudev	St James's University Hospital	Leeds	United Kingdom
Europe	Romania	Dana Mates	Victor Babes National Institute of Patology (INCDVB)	Bucharest	Romania
Europe	Croatia	Tomislav Kulis	University Hospital Centre (UHC) Zagreb	Zagreb	Croatia
Europe	Ukraine	Eduard Stakhovsky	National cancer institute	Kyiv	Ukraine

Europe	Greece	Elena Fountzilias	Hellenic Cooperative Oncology Group (HeCOG)	Athens	Greece
Europe	Bulgaria	Radka Kaneva	Medical University of Sofia	Sofia	Bulgaria
North America	Canada	Steve Gallinger	Mount Sinai Hospital	Toronto	Canada
North America	Canada	Jonathan Yeung	University Health Network	Toronto	Canada
North America	Canada	Riley Cox	Ontario Institute for Cancer Research	Toronto	Canada
North America	Canada	Lorenzo Ferri	McGill University	Montreal	Canada
North America	USA	Mark Purdue; Nat Rothman; Stephen Chanok	Division of Cancer Epidemiology and Genetics, NCI, NIH	Bethesda	USA
North America	USA	Samuel Antwi	Mayo Clinic	Florida	USA
South America	Brazil	Felipe Ribeiro Pinto	Brazilian National Cancer Institute	Rio de Janeiro	Brazil
South America	Brazil	Maria Paula Curado	A.C.Camargo Cancer Center	Sao Paulo	Brazil
South America	Brazil	Rui Reis	Barretos Cancer Institute	Barretos	Brazil
South America	Brazil	Patricia Ashton-Prolla	Hospital de Clinicas de Porto Alegre	Porto Alegre	Brazil
South America	Argentina	Carlos Vaccaro	Hospital Italiano	Buenos Aires	Argentina
South America	Colombia	Carolina Wiesner; Antonio Huertas Salgado	National Cancer Institute	Bogotá	Colombia

Appendix 2. Information and consent form

INTRODUCTION

You are requested to participate in a study to investigate environmental and genetic factors and their effects on the health of people. The study is being conducted by the Name of Local Collaborating Centre and an international research consortium including the International Agency for Research on Cancer and the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute. We obtained your name from your physician, who granted us approval to approach you about this study. Your participation in this study is voluntary. You may refuse to participate or withdraw from the study at any time without this affecting in any way the medical treatment that you are receiving. Please read this consent form thoroughly and ask the hospital coordinator any questions you may have about the study before signing.

EXPLANATION OF PROCEDURES

If you agree to participate in this study, you will be asked to participate in an interview survey and provide a blood sample. Pathology tissue samples collected at the time of your routine care will also be included. In addition, we will ask your permission to collect relevant information from your hospital records. No penalties will result if you decide not to respond, either to the information collection as a whole or to any particular question.

Questionnaire:

An interviewer will come to administer the questionnaire while you are in the hospital. The interview takes approximately 30 minutes and consists of questions related to lifestyle, environment and health.

Collection of blood and tissue Samples:

You will be asked to donate a blood sample while you are in the hospital. A trained nurse will take about 15 ml of blood from your arm in a routine manner. If available, we will request the Pathology Department in the hospital to provide a small sample of tissue from around your tumour.

What will your samples be used for:

Your blood and pathology tissue samples will be shipped to laboratories for analysis. The laboratory will not have any information regarding your identity, and biological samples obtained will be used for research purposes only. Any material not immediately used will continue to be stored for use in future studies to help scientists learn more about environment, genetic changes, and health. The research results are not suitable for use as clinical tests for your medical care. None of these samples will be tested for illegal drugs.

The genetic material from your samples (DNA) may undergo a procedure called whole-genome sequencing. This could determine many or all of the features of your DNA. We are interested only in results that are relevant to health research.

Your samples could be shared and shipped internationally for analysis within the framework of international collaboration.

Could any of the results be relevant and useful for your health:

It is possible that during the analyses of your samples the research team may find by chance genetic sequence results that suggest that you may have a higher risk of a genetically determined illness. However, unlike clinical investigations of genetic conditions, the information produced by the study is not reliable to make medical decisions; it is only valid for research purposes. For this reason, the research team will not provide any personal genetic results to the study participants. It is possible that your physician/hospital is interested in the research data produced and has the capacity to follow-up with additional testing. If this is possible, you will be able to discuss this option with your doctor, while keeping at any time the right to decide not to know about any results.

Sharing of data:

Your samples will be completely de-identified, meaning that scientific researchers will not be able to link them back to you. If you agree, we will allow results from genetic tests to be shared for scientific purposes.

COST AND COMPENSATION

There will be no cost to you for participating in this study, other than your time, and there is no compensation or payment for completing the questionnaire and providing biological samples.

POTENTIAL DISCOMFORT AND RISK

As for any blood collection, including those occurring during your routine clinical care, you may feel a little pain or develop a bruise on your arm at the puncture site. It is possible, but not likely, that there may be swelling or bleeding at the puncture site. There may be also uneasiness associated with needles. In the unlikely event of physical injury from drawing a blood sample, you will be provided with immediate medical treatment by the hospital personnel. Any samples of the tumour will be collected under normal clinical conditions.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS

This is a research study and there will be no direct benefits to you other than the satisfaction of participating in this research for the possible benefit of future generations. Your participation is very important to the success of this scientific research.

ASSURANCE OF CONFIDENTIALITY

The information concerning your participation in the study will be kept confidential and used only for scientific purposes, in accordance with applicable law of Name of Country. No one except members of the research team will have access to your answers. No one except members of the research team will have access to your test results, in addition to your doctor if you so decide that s/he is provided with research genetic data. Your employer will not be given any test results or information you provide us. Your biological samples will not be labelled with your name. Your name will not be used in any report or released in any way.

RIGHT TO WITHDRAW

Your participation in this medical research is voluntary and you may refuse to participate and/or withdraw your consent and discontinue participation at any time without penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled. If you initially decide to give permission to have biologic samples stored for future research purposes, but later change your mind by written notification to Name and address of local Principal Investigator, whatever remains of your biologic samples will then be destroyed. Your decision on this matter will not affect your medical care or employment.

CERTIFICATION

I have read the explanation about this study and have been given the opportunity to discuss it and to ask questions. By agreeing to participate in this study, I do not waive any rights that I may have regarding access to and disclosure of my records. I hereby consent to take part in the study components marked "yes" and refuse to consent to participate in the components marked "no". A copy of this consent form has been given to me.

YES	NO	Study Component
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Interview
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Blood Sample Collection and Testing
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tumour and peri-tumour tissue Collection and Testing
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Access to hospital records and registry records
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharing of genetic and cellular characteristics with other scientists for research purposes
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Sharing of genetic research data with your doctor

If we need to recontact you in the future to obtain extra information, would you agree to this?

Yes No

Signature of Participant	Date	Signature of Witness	Date

Print Name	Print Name

We appreciate your cooperation in this important research project. If you have further questions about this study, you may call Dr. (Name of Local Principal Investigator), at (Local Phone Number) or you may write to him/her at the following address:

Name of Local Collaborating Centre and Address

Appendix 3. Questionnaire

Identification data

The identification number should be used for the questionnaire and for any biological samples.

	<p>Stick here pre-printed label with ID number</p> <p>(see Annex_ 8 for details)</p> <p><i>Temporary handwritten ID if label not available at the time of the interview:</i></p> <p>.....</p>	
--	---	--

For local use only (optional) – information won't be entered in Mutographs database

Address:

.....

Telephone:

Email:

Full name of subject:

Hospital ID:

Date of interview: |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_| (DD/MM/YYYY)

Part 1: General information

1.1 |__| Sex (1=male, 2=female, 3=other/undisclosed)

1.2 |__|__| Ethnicity (codes to be defined)

If other, specify

Note to contributing study sites: list to be defined locally.

1.3 Date of birth - Day |__|__| Month |__|__| Year |__|__|__|__|

or (if date of birth not available, or not transferable):

|__|__| Age

1.4 |__| Highest education completed

- 0=none
- 1=primary
- 2=secondary
- 3=higher
- 9=Unknown/refuse to answer

1.5 |__|__| Age at completion of full-time education

1.6. Residential history. Answer R1-R3 for each place lived in for 1 year or longer.

Residential location starting from birth to present	R1. In what city or town did you live for 1 year or longer?	R2. During what period of time did you live in this location?	R3. What was the primary source of drinking water where you live?
1ST	<hr/> CODE* or CITY/COUNTY/COUNTRY <hr/> <input type="checkbox"/> RURAL <input type="checkbox"/> URBAN	__ __ __ __ START YEAR..... END YEAR __ __ __ __ START AGE..... END AGE	<input type="checkbox"/> Community supply <input type="checkbox"/> House-hold well <input type="checkbox"/> Bottled <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify
2ND	<hr/> CODE* or CITY/COUNTY/COUNTRY	__ __ __ __ START YEAR..... END YEAR __ __ __ __ START AGE..... END AGE	<input type="checkbox"/> Community supply <input type="checkbox"/> House-hold well <input type="checkbox"/> Bottled <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify

Residential location starting from birth to present	R1. In what city or town did you live for 1 year or longer?	R2. During what period of time did you live in this location?	R3. What was the primary source of drinking water where you live?
	<input type="checkbox"/> RURAL <input type="checkbox"/> URBAN		
3RD	<hr/> CODE* or CITY/COUNTY/COUNTRY <hr/> <input type="checkbox"/> RURAL <input type="checkbox"/> URBAN	_ _ _ _ START YEAR..... END YEAR _ _ _ _ START AGE..... END AGE	<input type="checkbox"/> Community supply <input type="checkbox"/> House-hold well <input type="checkbox"/> Bottled <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify
4TH	<hr/> CODE* or CITY/COUNTY/COUNTRY <hr/> <input type="checkbox"/> RURAL <input type="checkbox"/> URBAN	_ _ _ _ START YEAR..... END YEAR _ _ _ _ START AGE..... END AGE	<input type="checkbox"/> Community supply <input type="checkbox"/> House-hold well <input type="checkbox"/> Bottled <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify
5TH	<hr/> CODE* or CITY/COUNTY/COUNTRY <hr/> <input type="checkbox"/> RURAL <input type="checkbox"/> URBAN	_ _ _ _ START YEAR..... END YEAR	<input type="checkbox"/> Community supply <input type="checkbox"/> House-hold well <input type="checkbox"/> Bottled <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify

* Codes for Counties in Romania/ *Coduri pentru județe din România

Part 2: Body size

2.1 How tall are you?

2.1.1 Unit cm Feet/Inches

2.1.2 |_|_|_| cm OR |_| ft |_| in

2.2 How much do you weigh?

2.2.1 Unit kg Pounds

2.2.2 |_|_|_| kg OR |_|_|_| lb |_|_| oz

2.3 What is the most you have ever weighed? [For women: Do not include any times when you were pregnant.]

|_|_|_| kg OR |_|_|_| lb |_|_| oz

2.4 How much did you weigh about 2 years ago?

|_|_|_| kg OR |_|_|_| lb |_|_| oz

2.5 Have you recently experienced any involuntary/unexplained weight loss over the past year?

- No
- Yes
- Unknown

Part 3: Medical history

3.1 Have you ever had any of the following diseases confirmed by a doctor? To interviewer: list all diseases one by one.

(0=definitely or probably No; 1=definitely or probably Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes: - How old were you (approximately) when it was first diagnosed?

- Were you prescribed a treatment by a doctor?

(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

		Age	Treatment
3.1.1	_ Diabetes	_ _	_
3.1.2	_ Pancreatitis	_ _	_
3.1.3	_ Crohn's disease	_ _	_
3.1.4	_ Ulcerative colitis	_ _	_
3.1.5	_ Hypertension	_ _	_
3.1.6	_ Chronic kidney disease	_ _	_
3.1.7	_ Kidney stones	_ _	_
3.1.8	_ Asthma	_ _	_
3.1.9	_ Allergies	_ _	_
3.1.10	_ Colorectal polyps	_ _	_
3.1.11	_ Cholangitis	_ _	_
3.1.12	_ Hereditary genetic disorder	_ _	_
If yes, which of the following <input type="checkbox"/> Lynch syndrome (hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer: HNPCC) <input type="checkbox"/> Familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP) <input type="checkbox"/> von Hippel-Lindau syndrome (VHL) <input type="checkbox"/> Birt-Hogg-Dubé syndrome (BHD) <input type="checkbox"/> Hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndrome <input type="checkbox"/> Peutz-Jeghers syndrome <input type="checkbox"/> Other (Specify:) 			
3.1.13	_ Cancer	_ _	_

If yes: site of origin |__|__|

(1=mouth or pharynx, 2=oesophagus, 3=stomach, 4=colon or rectum, 5=pancreas, 6=liver, 7=larynx, 8=lung, 9=melanoma, 10=breast, 11=cervix of uterus, 12=other uterus, 13=prostate, 14=bladder, 15=kidney, 16=thyroid gland, 17=leukaemia and lymphoma, 18=other, unknown or more than one site)

3.2 Have you regularly (at least once a week for a year) taken any medication for the past year? (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

3.2.1 |__| Anti-diabetic

3.2.2 |__| Anti-blood pressure

3.2.3 |__| Analgesic of the type nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, NSAIDs (e.g., aspirin, ibuprofen, naproxen)

3.3 |__| Have you regularly taken any herbal remedies?
(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes: |__| Was it prescribed by a doctor?
(0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

Can you describe the herbal remedies taken and/or provide name of the treatment?

.....
.....

3.4 |__| How many times have you had X-rays procedures (for medical examinations or radiation treatments), including for X-rays required by your employers? (do not include dental X-rays)

- 1=never
- 2=1-4 times
- 3=5-9 times
- 4=10 times or more
- 9=unknown/refuse to answer

FOR COLORECTUM ONLY

3.5 Were you breastfed? |__|

1=no

2=yes, number of months |__|

3.6 Type of delivery at your birth |__|

1=natural childbirth

2=caesarean section

3.7 Do you take antibiotics? |__|

1=no

2=yes

9=unknown/refuse to answer

3.8 In the past, what is the TOTAL amount of time you used antibiotics? |__|

(1) None

(2) Less than 15 days

(3) 15 days to 2 months

(4) 2 to 4 months

(5) 4 months to 2 years

(6) 2 to 3 years

(7) 3+ years

3.9 Have you ever had a septicaemia caused by E. coli? |__|

1=Yes

2= No

Part 4: Family history

4.1 Please list the number of brothers, sisters, sons and daughters that you have (exclude step-brothers and step-sisters):

Brothers |__| Sisters |__| Sons |__| Daughters |__|

4.2 |__| Did any of your close relatives (those listed above plus your parents) ever suffer from cancer? (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=unknown/refuse to answer)

If yes:

Relative (code 1-6)	Age at diagnosis	Cancer (text)	site	Cancer (ICD-10 code)	site
(1) Father (2) Mother (3) Brother (4) Sister (5) Son (6) Daughter					
__	__ __			C __ __ . __	
__	__ __			C __ __ . __	
__	__ __			C __ __ . __	
__	__ __			C __ __ . __	
__	__ __			C __ __ . __	
__	__ __			C __ __ . __	

Part 5: Tobacco*

This question relates to your tobacco smoking habits before you recently became ill.

5.1 |__| Did you smoke cigarettes in the past year? (0=No, 1=Yes, 9=refuse to answer)

If yes:

5.1.1 |__|__| How many cigarettes per day on average? (ignore pipe or cigar smoking; "cigarettes" include handrolled and "papirosi")

5.1.2 |__|__| At what age did you start smoking? (i.e. using cigarettes on most days)

5.1.3 |__|__| How many years have you smoked?

If no:

5.1.4 |__| Have you ever smoked cigarettes on most days for at least one year?
(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=refuse to answer)

[If no, go to question 5.2]

5.1.5 |__|__| How many cigarettes did you smoke per day on average? (ignore pipe and cigar smoking; "cigarettes" include handrolled)

5.1.6 |__|__| At what age did you start smoking? (i.e. using cigarettes on most days)

5.1.7 |__|__| At what age did you stop smoking?

5.2 Do you smoke, or have you ever regularly smoked, other tobacco products?

No

Yes, current cigar smoker

Yes, current pipe smoker

Yes, current water-pipe smoker

Refuse to answer

Yes, ex-cigar smoker

Yes, ex-pipe smoker

Yes, ex-water-pipe smoker

Part 6: Alcohol

This question relates to your alcohol drinking habits before you recently became ill.

6.1 |__| Do you drink any alcohol? (0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Refuse to answer)

If yes:

6.1.1 |__| How many days/week would you have some alcohol?
(0-7) (0 means none in most weeks)

6.1.2 |__| How many days/week would you have some alcohol before noon?
(0-7) (0 means none in most weeks)

6.1.3 How much of the following alcoholic beverages do you usually drink per week?
To interviewer: If a range is given (eg 2 or 3 bottles) then enter the upper end of the range. (0=None at all)

6.1.3.1 Whiskey/vodka or other strong drinks (40% ethanol) -
Quantity/week : |__|__|__|__| - Unit glasses bottles

6.1.3.2 Wine
Quantity/week : __|__|__|__| - Unit glasses bottles

6.1.3.3 Beer |__|__| bottles/week

If no (i.e. non-drinker over the past year):

6.2 |__| Have you ever used alcohol at least once a month for a year?
(0=No, 1=Yes, 9=Refuse to answer) [If 0 or 9, go to question 7.1]

If yes:

6.2.1 |__| How many days/week would you have some alcohol?
(0-7) (0 means none in most weeks)

6.2.2 |__| How many days/week would you have some alcohol before noon?
(0-7) (0 means none in most weeks)

6.2.3 How much of the following alcoholic beverages do you usually drink per week?
To interviewer: If a range is given (eg 2 or 3 bottles) then enter the upper end of the range (0=None at all).

6.2.3.1 Whiskey/vodka or other strong drinks (40% ethanol)
Quantity/week : |__|__|__|__| - Unit glasses bottles

6.2.3.2 Wine
Quantity/week : |__|__|__|__| - Unit glasses bottles

6.2.3.3 Beer |__|__| bottles/week

6.2.4 |__|__| Years since you last drank alcohol regularly

Note to contributing study sites: "glasses", i.e. standard drink volume, and "bottle" volumes to be defined locally.

Part 7: Diet

7.1 How often do you usually eat the following food items?

7.1.1 Red meat (i.e. beef, veal, pork, lamb, mutton, horse, and goat meat)

If red meat consumed:

7.1.1.1 Boiled meat

7.1.1.2 Charcoal-grilled meat (cooked on barbecue or equivalent)

7.1.1.3 Roasted meat

7.1.1.4 Fried meat

7.1.1.5 Other, Specify:.....

7.1.2 Poultry (i.e. chicken and turkey)

7.1.3 Processed* meat, including hams, salami, sausages, etc.

7.1.4 Fish

If fish consumed:

7.1.4.1 Fresh fish

7.1.4.2 Processed* fish

7.1.5 Fresh fruits (i.e. apples, pears, orange and other citrus fruits, bananas, berries, etc., when in season)

7.1.6 Raw vegetables (i.e. green salads, tomatoes, etc., when in season)

7.1.7 Cooked green/leafy vegetables (i.e. spinach, artichokes, asparagus, green beans, etc., when in season)

7.1.8 Dairy products (i.e. milk, yoghurts, cheese, butter, etc.)

7.1.9 Cookies, biscuits, chocolates, cakes and sweets

7.1.10 Soft drinks (e.g., cola)

1=never

2=less than once a month

3=1-3 times a month

4=once or twice a week

5=most days but not every days

6=every day

9=unknown/refuse to answer

*Salted, smoked, or processed with any other preservation method.

Part 8: Occupation history

Please list below any occupations or jobs you have held for at least 10 years. Include time spent on farm as an occupation. If you had more than one occupation for 10 years or more, then start with the first job you had after you left school.

OCCUPATION NUMBER 1

8.1 From: year |__|__|__|__| to year |__|__|__|__|

and/or

From: age |__|__| to age |__|__|

8.2 Occupation / Job title:

.....

8.3 Main activity of the company [if self-employed, state so]:

.....

.....

8.4 Your main type of activity at this job:

.....

8.5 Were you exposed to any chemicals or products listed below? (0=No; 1=Yes; 9=Don't know)

|__| Pesticides

|__| Engine exhaust

|__| Solvents

|__| Metal dust

|__| Ionizing radiation

If yes to any: Specify.....

Any other exposure you would like to list:

.....

8.6 |__| How physically strenuous was this job?

(1) Very limited physical activity - mainly indoor clerical work

(2) Some physical activity - extended periods of time standing up. Some lifting, etc.

(3) Physical active work - mainly standing up. Lots of outdoor work. Some lifting, etc.

(4) Very physically active - strenuous efforts frequently required.

[Repeat above questions for as many occupations as necessary]

Part 9: Non-occupational physical activity

This question relates to your physical activity habits at home or for leisure before you recently became ill (include walking for exercise, running, swimming gym, team sports). Even if this was in the past, please include it.

9.1 |__| Do/did you exercise regularly (at least 30 mins per week)?
(0) Never; (1) Yes, still; (2) Yes, only in the past; (9) unknown/refuse to answer

If yes (current and past)

9.1.1 How often is/was it?

9.1.1.1 |__|__| weeks per year

9.1.1.2 |__|__| number of times per week

9.1.2 |__|__| How long is/was it? (min each time)

9.1.3 |__| How intensive is/was it?

- (1) Low=no increase in heart beat, and no perspiration
- (2) Moderate=increase the heart beat slightly with some light perspiration
- (3) Vigorous= increase the heart beat substantially with heavy sweating

If only in the past

9.1.4 |__|__| How old were you when you stopped regular exercise (eg less than weekly)?

9.1.5 |__| On a typical day, how much time would you spend exercising?

- (1) less than 30 minutes
- (2) between 30 minutes to one hour
- (3) between one hour and two hours
- (4) two hours or more

9.2 |__| Are/were you physically active daily due to household activities, such as grocery shopping and supplying the house with first needs, looking after children, gardening, etc. (at least two hours per day)?
(0) Never; (1) Yes, still; (2) Yes, only in the past; (9) unknown/refuse to answer

Part 10: (for women only) Reproductive, menstrual, and use of hormones history

10.1 |__| Have you ever given birth? (please consider pregnancies that lasted at least 5 months)
(0) Never; (1) Yes; (9) unknown/refuse to answer

If yes:

10.1.1 |__|__| How many babies have you had? (please consider babies born alive or dead after 5 months pregnancy)

10.1.2 |__| Did you breastfeed your children?
(0) No; (1) Yes; (9) unknown/refuse to answer

10.2 At what age did your first menstrual periods begin?

- | | |
|--|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Never menstruated | <input type="checkbox"/> 13 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 9 or younger | <input type="checkbox"/> 14 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 10 | <input type="checkbox"/> 15 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 11 | <input type="checkbox"/> 16 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 12 | <input type="checkbox"/> 17 or older |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Don't know | |

10.3 Are you still having menstrual periods or have they stopped?

- Still having menstrual periods
- Not sure, periods are irregular or using hormone supplements
- Menstrual periods have stopped permanently

10.4 |__|__| (if menstrual periods have stopped) How old were you when your menstrual periods stopped permanently?

10.5 |__| Have you ever used oral contraceptives?
(0) Never; (1) Yes, still; (2) Yes, only in the past

If yes (current and past):

10.5.1 |__|__| How old were you when you began using oral contraceptives?

10.5.2 |__|__| For how many years did you use oral contraceptives?

Note to contributing study sites: How relevant would it be to have questions on HRT?

Comments :

Appendix 4. Anthropometric measures, blood pressure, and other clinical information

Anthropometric measures are taken from the case (height, weight, blood pressure) and additional clinical information is collected from the clinical notes

ID No. |__|__|__|__|__|__|__|__|__| (Stick here pre-printed label with ID number) *Temporary handwritten ID if label not available at the time of the interview* (see Annex_ 8 for details)

1. Demographic information [if unavailable from questionnaire]

1.1 |__| Sex (1=male, 2=female, 3=other/undisclosed)

1.2 Date of birth - Day |__|__| Month |__|__| Year |__|__|__|__|

or (if date of birth not available, or not transferable):

|__|__| Age

2. Anthropometric measures

Measurements should be taken without shoes and in loose clothing.

Waist and hip measurement should follow the guidelines provided in WHO Stepwise approach to surveillance (STEPS) (WHO, Geneva, World Health Organization (WHO), 2008). Waist measurement is to be made at the approximate midpoint between the lower margin of the last palpable rib and the top of the iliac crest and hip circumference measurement must be taken around the widest portion of the buttocks. The tape should be snug around the body, but not pulled so tight that it is constricting. For the measurements, the subject stands with arms at the sides, feet positioned close together, and weight evenly distributed across the feet. The waist circumference should be measured at the end of a normal expiration, when the lungs are at their functional residual capacity.

Height: Unit cm Feet/Inches

|__|__|__| cm OR |__| ft |__| in

Weight Unit kg Pounds

|__|__|__| kg OR |__|__|__| lb |__|__| oz

Waist: |__|__|__| cm OR |__| ft |__| in

Hip: |__|__|__| cm OR |__| ft |__| in

3. Blood pressure

Blood pressure should be measured while the patient is seated.

(SBP: Systolic blood pressure / DBP: Diastolic blood pressure; in mmHg)

SBP/DBP :..... /.....

4. Medical history and known genetic syndromes [if unavailable from questionnaire] – Select all that apply, and indicate age at first symptoms:

Disease..... Age at first symptoms

Diabetes..... |__|__|

Pancreatitis..... |__|__|

Crohn's disease..... |__|__|

Ulcerative colitis..... |__|__|

Hypertension..... |__|__|

Chronic kidney disease..... |__|__|

Kidney stones..... |__|__|

Asthma..... |__|__|

Allergies..... |__|__|

Colorectal polyps..... |__|__|

Gastroesophageal reflux disease..... |__|__|

Cholangitis..... |__|__|

Hereditary genetic disorder..... |__|__|

If yes, which of the followings:

Lynch syndrome (hereditary nonpolyposis colorectal cancer: HNPCC)

Familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP)

von Hippel-Lindau syndrome (VHL)

Birt-Hogg-Dubé syndrome (BHD)

Hereditary breast and ovarian cancer syndrome

Peutz-Jeghers syndrome

Other

Cancer..... |__|__|

If yes: site of origin |__|__|

(1=mouth or pharynx, 2=oesophagus, 3=stomach, 4=colon or rectum, 5=pancreas, 6=liver, 7=larynx, 8=lung, 9=melanoma, 10=breast, 11=cervix of uterus, 12=other uterus, 13=prostate, 14=bladder, 15=kidney, 16=thyroid gland, 17=leukaemia and lymphoma, 18=other, unknown or more than one site)

5. Family history of cancer [if unavailable from questionnaire] – Report known familial cancer cases amongst first degree relatives (parents, siblings, offspring):

Relative (code 1-6)	Age at diagnosis	Cancer site (text)	Cancer site (ICD-10 code)
(1) Father			
(2) Mother			
(3) Brother			
(4) Sister			
(5) Son			
(6) Daughter			
_	_ _		C _ _ . _
_	_ _		C _ _ . _
_	_ _		C _ _ . _
_	_ _		C _ _ . _
_	_ _		C _ _ . _
_	_ _		C _ _ . _

6. Tobacco smoking habits [if unavailable questionnaire]

- Current smoker
- Ex-smoker
- Never smoker
- Unknown

COMMENTS:

.....

.....

Appendix 5. Biosample logsheet

ID No. |__|__|__|__|__|__|__|__|__| (Stick here pre-printed label with ID number) *Temporary handwritten ID if label not available at the time of the interview (see Annex_8 for details)*

Cancer type : |__|

- 1 = colorectal
- 2 = oesophageal squamous
- 3 = oesophageal adenocarcinoma
- 4 = pancreatic
- 5 = renal

Case status : |__|

- 1 = confirmed
- 2 = not confirmed
- 3 = pending diagnosis

Collected materials

1. BLOOD

1.1. Whole Blood:

- 1.1.1 Number of samples |__|
- 1.1.2 Collection date |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)
- 1.1.3 Fasting Y/N |__|
- 1.1.4 Date sent to IARC |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)

1.2. "Processed Blood":

- 1.2.1 Number of Plasma |__|
- 1.2.2 Number of RBC (Red Blood Cells) |__|
- 1.2.3 Number of BC (Buffy Coat) |__|
- 1.2.4 Collection date |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)
- 1.2.5 Fasting Y/N |__|
- 1.2.6 Date sent to IARC |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)

2. SOLID TUMOR

2.1. Tumour biopsy

2.1.1 Number of samples |__|

2.1.2 Collection date |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)

2.1.3 Preservation mode |__|

- 1 = snap freezing;
- 2 = Preservation in RNAlater;
- 3 = other, specify_____

2.1.4 H&E FFPE slide Y/N |__|

2.1.5 Date sent to IARC |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)

2.2 Tumour resection

2.2.1 Number of samples |__|

2.2.2 Collection date |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)

2.2.3 Preservation mode |__|

- 1 = snap freezing;
- 2 =preservation in RNAlater;
- 3 = other, specify_____

2.2.4 Delay from resection to sampling (min) |__|__|__|

2.2.5 Pre-treatment Y/N |__|

2.2.6 H&E FFPE slide Y/N |__|

2.2.7 Date sent to IARC |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)

2.3 Peri-tumour

2.3.1 Number of samples |__|

2.3.2 Collection date |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)

2.3.3 Preservation mode |__|

- 1 = snap freezing;
- 2 = preservation in RNAlater;
- 3 = other, specify_____

2.3.4 Date sent to IARC |__|__|/|__|__|/|__|__| (DD/MM/YY)

3.COMMENTS:

3.1.1.1. date of surgery (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

3.1.2. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy followed by surgery

3.1.3. Chemotherapy

If yes,

3.1.3.1. date of start (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

3.1.3.2. duration (months) |_|_|_|

3.1.4. Radiotherapy

If yes,

3.1.4.1. date of start (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

3.1.4.2. duration (months) |_|_|_|

3.1.5. Other (specify) (example: palliative care)

3.1.6. Unknown

3.2 Synchronous (same period of diagnosis) primary cancers. Does the patient have:

3.2.1. Any solid tumour (other than index cancer) Yes No Unknown

If yes, specify site of other tumour:

3.2.2. Leukaemia Yes No Unknown

3.2.3. Lymphoma Yes No Unknown

3.3 Pathology information:

3.3.1. Nephrectomy procedure: Partial Radical

3.3.2. Laterality: Right Left Not specified

3.3.3. Tumour site: Upper pole Middle pole
 Lower pole Other (Specify:.....)
 Not specified

3.3.4. Tumour focality: Unifocal Multifocal

3.3.5. Tumour size: Greatest dimension: ...|_|_|.cm

If multifocal,

cumulative tumour size (sum of max tumour diameters for all tumours present): |_|_|.cm

3.3.6. Histologic type

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Clear cell renal cell carcinoma (RCC)	4 <input type="checkbox"/> Carcinoma of the collecting duct of Bellini
2 <input type="checkbox"/> Papillary RCC	5 <input type="checkbox"/> RCC, unclassified
3 <input type="checkbox"/> Chromophobe RCC	6 <input type="checkbox"/> Other (Specify:.....)

Morphology, according to ICD-O3, 2000: |_|_|_|_|/|_| Specify:.....

3.3.7. Sarcomatous features: Not identified Present

3.3.8. Tumor necrosis: Not identified Present

3.3.9. Histologic Grade (Fuhrman system):

- Not applicable Grade X (cannot be assessed)
- Grade 1, Nuclei round, uniform, approximately 10 µm; nucleoli inconspicuous or absent
- Grade 2, Nuclei slightly irregular, approximately 15 µm; nucleoli evident
- Grade 3, Nuclei very irregular, approximately 20 µm; nucleoli large and prominent
- Grade 4, Nuclei bizarre and multilobated, 20 µm or greater, nucleoli prominent, chromatin clumped

3.3.10. Lympho-vascular invasion: Yes No Cannot be assessed

3.4. Pathological and clinical staging information (TNM system, 8th edition):

Fill in the following table, using both medical charts and pathological reports, to report clinical and pathological staging, respectively. Strive to report TNM prior neoadjuvant therapy.

KIDNEY STAGING FORM		
CLINICAL <i>Extent of disease before any treatment</i>		PATHOLOGICAL <i>Extent of disease through completion of definitive surgery</i>
	PRIMARY TUMOR (T)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tx	Primary tumor cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Tx
<input type="checkbox"/> T0	No evidence of primary tumor	<input type="checkbox"/> T0

<input type="checkbox"/> T1	Tumor 7cm or less in greatest dimension, limited to the kidney	<input type="checkbox"/> T1
<input type="checkbox"/> T1a	Tumor 4cm or less in greatest dimension, limited to the kidney	<input type="checkbox"/> T1a
<input type="checkbox"/> T1b	Tumor more than 4cm but not more than 7cm in greatest dimension, limited to the kidney	<input type="checkbox"/> T1b
<input type="checkbox"/> T2	Tumor more than 7cm in greatest dimension, limited to the kidney	<input type="checkbox"/> T2
<input type="checkbox"/> T2a	Tumor more than 7cm but less than or equal to 10cm in greatest dimension, limited to the kidney	<input type="checkbox"/> T2a
<input type="checkbox"/> T2b	Tumor more than 10cm in greatest dimension, limited to the kidney	<input type="checkbox"/> T2b
<input type="checkbox"/> T3	Tumor extends into major veins or perinephric tissues but not into the ipsilateral adrenal gland and not beyond Gerota's fascia	<input type="checkbox"/> T3
<input type="checkbox"/> T3a	Tumor grossly extends into the renal vein or its segmental (muscle containing) branches, or tumor invades perirenal and/or renal sinus fat but not beyond Gerota's fascia	<input type="checkbox"/> T3a
<input type="checkbox"/> T3b	Tumor grossly extends into the vena cava below the diaphragm	<input type="checkbox"/> T3b
<input type="checkbox"/> T3c	Tumor grossly extends into the vena cava above the diaphragm or invades the wall of the vena cava	<input type="checkbox"/> T3c
<input type="checkbox"/> T4	Tumor invades beyond Gerota's fascia (including contiguous extension into the ipsilateral adrenal gland)	<input type="checkbox"/> T4
REGIONAL LYMPH NODES (N)		
<input type="checkbox"/> Nx	Regional lymph node cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Nx
<input type="checkbox"/> N0	No regional lymph node metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> N0
<input type="checkbox"/> N1	Regional lymph node metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> N1
DISTANT METASTASIS (M)		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mx	Distant metastasis cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Mx
<input type="checkbox"/> M0	No distant metastasis (no pathological M0; use clinical M to complete stage group)	<input type="checkbox"/> M0
<input type="checkbox"/> M1	Distant metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> M1
If M1, site(s) of metastasis:	

3.5. Comments :

4. FOR PANCREAS ONLY

4.1 Treatment information:

4.1.1. Surgery (removal of tumor)

If yes,

date of surgery (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

4.1.2. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy followed by surgery

4.1.3. Chemotherapy

If yes,

date of start (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

duration (months) |_|_|_|

4.1.4. Radiotherapy

If yes,

date of start (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

duration (months) |_|_|_|

4.1.5. Other (specify) (example: palliative care)

4.1.6. Unknown

4.2 Synchronous (same period of diagnosis) primary cancers. Does the patient have:

4.2.1. Any solid tumor (other than index cancer) Yes No Unknown

If yes, specify site of other tumor:

4.2.2. Leukaemia Yes No Unknown

4.2.3. Lymphoma Yes No Unknown

4.3 Pathology information:

4.3.1. Specimen: Head Body Tail CNB No. of biopsies |_|_|

Other (Specify:.....)

4.3.2. Procedure:

- Pancreaticoduodenectomy (Whipple Resection), total pancreatectomy
- Pancreaticoduodenectomy (Whipple Resection), partial pancreatectomy
- Partial pancreatectomy, body
- Partial pancreatectomy, tail

Not specified

Other, specify

4.3.3. Tumor site: Head Body Tail Overlapping lesion Cannot be determined

4.3.4 Greatest tumor dimension: |__|__| cm

4.3.4. Histologic type and subtype and grade:

Morphology, according to ICD-O3, 2000 |__|__|__|__|/|__| Specify:.....

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Ductal adenocarcinoma	5 <input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma
2 <input type="checkbox"/> Signet ring carcinoma	6 <input type="checkbox"/> Hepatoid carcinoma
3 <input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma	7 <input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma
4 <input type="checkbox"/> Colloid carcinoma	8 <input type="checkbox"/> Other (Specify:.....)

4.3.6a Histologic Grade: (WHO 2010)

Not applicable Grade X (cannot be assessed)

Grade 1, Well differentiated glandular structures; intensive mucin production; up to 5 mitoses/10HPF; little nuclear polymorphism and polar arrangement of nuclei.

Grade 2, Moderately differentiated duct-like structures and tubular glands; irregular mucin production; 6-10 mitoses/10HPF; moderate nuclear polymorphism.

Grade 3, Poorly differentiated glands; abortive mucin production; >10 mitoses/10HPF; marked nuclear polymorphism and increased nuclear size.

4.3.6b. Histologic Grade (CAP: College of American Pathologists, 2016):

Not applicable Grade X (cannot be assessed)

Grade 1, Well differentiated

Grade 2, Moderately differentiated

Grade 3, Poorly differentiated

Grade 4, Undifferentiated

4.3.7. Specify the applied grading system:

WHO grading 2010

CAP 2016

4.3.8. Perineural invasion: Yes No Cannot be determined

4.3.9. Lympho-vascular invasion: Yes No Cannot be determined

4.4 Pathological and clinical staging information (TNM system, 8th edition):

Fill in the following table, using both medical charts and pathological reports, to report clinical and pathological staging, respectively. Strive to report TNM prior neoadjuvant therapy.

PANCREAS STAGING FORM		
CLINICAL <i>Extent of disease before any treatment</i>		PATHOLOGICAL <i>Extent of disease through completion of definitive surgery</i>
	PRIMARY TUMOR (T)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tx	Primary tumor cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Tx
<input type="checkbox"/> T0	No evidence of primary tumor	<input type="checkbox"/> T0
<input type="checkbox"/> Tis	Carcinoma <i>in situ</i> *	<input type="checkbox"/> Tis
<input type="checkbox"/> T1	Tumor limited to the pancreas, 2cm or less in greatest dimension	<input type="checkbox"/> T1
<input type="checkbox"/> T2	Tumor limited to the pancreas, more than 2cm in greatest dimension	<input type="checkbox"/> T2
<input type="checkbox"/> T3	Tumor extends beyond the pancreas but without involvement of the celiac axis or the superior mesenteric artery	<input type="checkbox"/> T3
<input type="checkbox"/> T4	Tumor involves the celiac axis or the superior mesenteric artery (unresectable primary tumor)	<input type="checkbox"/> T4
	<i>*Note: Tis also includes the "PanInIII" classification</i>	
	REGIONAL LYMPH NODES (N)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Nx	Regional lymph node cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Nx
<input type="checkbox"/> N0	No regional lymph node metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> N0

<input type="checkbox"/> N1	Regional lymph node metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> N1
	DISTANT METASTASIS (M)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Mx	Distant metastasis cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Mx
<input type="checkbox"/> M0	No distant metastasis (no pathological M0; use clinical M to complete stage group)	<input type="checkbox"/> M0
<input type="checkbox"/> M1	Distant metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> M1
If M1, site(s) of metastasis:	

4.5 Comments:

5. FOR OESOPHAGUS ONLY

5.1 Treatment information:

5.1.1. Surgery (removal of tumor)

If yes,

5.1.1.1. date of surgery (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

5.1.2. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy followed by surgery

5.1.3. Chemotherapy

If yes,

5.1.3.1 date of start (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

5.1.3.2 duration (months) |_|_|_|

5.1.4. Radiotherapy

If yes,

5.1.4.1 date of start (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

5.1.4.2 duration (months) |_|_|_|

5.1.5. Other (specify) (example: palliative care)

5.1.6. Unknown

5.2 Synchronous (same period of diagnosis) primary cancers. Does the patient have:

5.2.1. Any solid tumor (other than index cancer) Yes No Unknown

If yes, specify site of other tumor:

5.2.2. Leukaemia Yes No Unknown

5.2.3. Lymphoma Yes No Unknown

5.3 Pathology information:

5.3.1. Procedure:

Endoscopic Biopsy No. of biopsies: |__|__|

Esophagectomy

Esophagogastrostomy

Other (Specify:.....)

5.3.2. Tumor site:

Cervical (proximal) oesophagus

Mid-oesophagus

Distal oesophagus

Oesophagogastric junction (GEJ), only those originated from lower oesophagus or junction,

to be determined by the endoscopist/surgeon

5.3.3. Relationship of tumor to GEJ:

Tumor is entirely located within the tubular oesophagus and does not involve the GEJ

Tumor midpoint lies in the distal oesophagus *and* involves the GEJ

Tumor midpoint is located at the GEJ

Tumor midpoint lies in the proximal stomach or cardia and involves the GEJ

Not specified

Cannot be assessed

5.3.4. Tumor size: Greatest dimension: |__|__|.cm cannot be determined

5.3.5. Histologic type:

Morphology, according to ICD-O3, 2000: |__|__|__|__|/|__| Specify:.....

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma	6 <input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma
2 <input type="checkbox"/> Squamous cell carcinoma	7 <input type="checkbox"/> Carcinoma, type cannot be determined
3 <input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma	8 <input type="checkbox"/> Basaloid SCC

4 <input type="checkbox"/> Verrucous carcinoma	9 <input type="checkbox"/> Other (Specify:.....)
5 <input type="checkbox"/> Spindle cell carcinoma	

5.3.6. Histologic Grade:

- Grade X: Cannot be assessed
- Grade 1: Well differentiated
- Grade 2: Moderately differentiated
- Grade 3: Poorly differentiated
- Grade 4: Undifferentiated

5.3.7. Lympho-vascular invasion: Yes No Cannot be assessed

5.3.8. Perineural invasion: Yes No Cannot be assessed

5.4 Pathological and clinical staging information (TNM system, 8th edition):

Fill in the following table, using both medical charts and pathological reports, to report clinical and pathological staging, respectively. Strive to report TNM prior neoadjuvant therapy.

OESOPHAGUS STAGING FORM		
CLINICAL <i>Extent of disease before any treatment</i>		PATHOLOGICAL <i>Extent of disease through completion of definitive surgery</i>
	PRIMARY TUMOR (T)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tx	Primary tumor cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Tx
<input type="checkbox"/> T0	No evidence of primary tumor	<input type="checkbox"/> T0
<input type="checkbox"/> Tis	High-grade dysplasia*	
<input type="checkbox"/> T1	Tumor invades lamina propria, muscularis mucosae, or submucosa	<input type="checkbox"/> T1
<input type="checkbox"/> T1a	Tumor invades lamina propria or muscularis mucosae	<input type="checkbox"/> T1a
<input type="checkbox"/> T1b	Tumor invades submucosa	<input type="checkbox"/> T1b

<input type="checkbox"/> T2	Tumor invades muscularis propria	<input type="checkbox"/> T2
<input type="checkbox"/> T3	Tumor invades adventitia	<input type="checkbox"/> T3
<input type="checkbox"/> T4	Tumor invades adjacent structures	<input type="checkbox"/> T4
<input type="checkbox"/> T4a	Resectable tumor invading pleura, pericardium, or diaphragm	<input type="checkbox"/> T4a
<input type="checkbox"/> T4b	Unresectable tumor invading other adjacent structures, such as aorta, vertebral body, trachea, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/> T4b
	*High-grade dysplasia includes all non-invasive neoplastic epithelium that was formerly called carcinoma in situ, a diagnosis that is no longer used for columnar mucosae anywhere in the gastrointestinal tract.	
	REGIONAL LYMPH NODES (N)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Nx	Regional lymph node cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Nx
<input type="checkbox"/> N0	No regional lymph node metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> N0
<input type="checkbox"/> N1	Regional lymph node metastases involving 1 to 2 nodes	<input type="checkbox"/> N1
<input type="checkbox"/> N2	Regional lymph node metastases involving 3 to 6 nodes	<input type="checkbox"/> N2
<input type="checkbox"/> N3	Regional lymph node metastases involving 7 or more nodes	<input type="checkbox"/> N3
	DISTANT METASTASIS (M)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Mx	Distant metastasis cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Mx
<input type="checkbox"/> M0	No distant metastasis (no pathological M0; use clinical M to complete stage group)	<input type="checkbox"/> M0
<input type="checkbox"/> M1	Distant metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> M1
If M1, site(s) of metastasis:	

5.5 Comments:

6. FOR COLORECTUM ONLY

6.1. Treatment information:

6.1.1. Surgery (removal of tumor)

If yes, date of surgery (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

6.1.2. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy followed by surgery

6.1.3. Chemotherapy

If yes,

6.1.3.1 date of start (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

6.1.3.2 duration (months) |_|_|_|

6.1.4. Radiotherapy

If yes,

6.1.4.1 date of start (DD/MM/YYYY): |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

6.1.4.2 duration (months) |_|_|_|

6.1.5. Other (specify) (example: palliative care)

6.1.6. Unknown

NB: if neoadjuvant treatment has been done before tumor sample collection, the case will not be eligible for Mutographs

6.2. Synchronous (same period of diagnosis) primary cancers. Does the patient have:

6.2.1. Any solid tumor (other than index cancer) Yes No Unknown

If yes, specify site of other tumor:

6.2.2. Leukaemia Yes No Unknown

6.2.3. Lymphoma Yes No Unknown

6.3. Pathology information:

6.3.1. Procedures:

Excisional biopsy (polypectomy) Total Colectomy Partial colectomy
 Rectal resection Colonoscopic biopsy (No. of biopsies: |_|_|)

6.3.2. Tumor site:

Cecum Right (ascending) colon Hepatic flexure Transverse colon
 Splenic flexure Left (descending) colon Sigmoid Rectum
 Colon, not specified Other, (Specify:.....)

Please fill up parts 6.3.3-6.3.5 if the specimen is a polypectomy, go to part 6.3.6 if the specimen is colectomy and leave parts 6.3.3-6.3.5 blank; go to part 6.3.7 if the specimen is a biopsy:

6.3.3. Polyp size: Greatest dimension: |__|__| cm

6.3.4. Type of polyp in which invasive carcinoma arose:

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Tubular adenoma | <input type="checkbox"/> Villous adenoma |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Tubulovillous adenoma | <input type="checkbox"/> Traditional serrated adenoma |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sessile serrated adenoma | <input type="checkbox"/> Serrated polyp, unclassified |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Hamartomatous polyp | <input type="checkbox"/> Other, (Specify:) |

6.3.5. Size of invasive carcinoma in the polyp: Greatest dimension: |__|__| cm

6.3.6. Tumor size: Greatest dimension: |__|__| cm

6.3.7. Histologic type:

Morphology, according to ICD-O3, 2000: |__|__|__|__|/|__| Specify:.....

1 <input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma	7 <input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma
2 <input type="checkbox"/> Mucinous adenocarcinoma	8 <input type="checkbox"/> Serrated adenocarcinoma
3 <input type="checkbox"/> Signet-ring adenocarcinoma	9 <input type="checkbox"/> Micropapillary carcinoma
4 <input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma	10 <input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma
5 <input type="checkbox"/> Squamous cell carcinoma	11 <input type="checkbox"/> Other (Specify:.....)
6 <input type="checkbox"/> Spindle cell carcinoma	12 <input type="checkbox"/> Carcinoma, type cannot be determined

6.3.8. Histologic Grade:

- Cannot be assessed
- Low grade (well differentiated to moderately differentiated)
- High grade (poorly differentiated to undifferentiated)

6.3.9. Lympho-vascular invasion: Yes No

6.3.10. Perineural invasion: Yes No

6.3.11. Additional pathologic findings: None identified Inflammatory bowel disease
 Other (specify):

6.4. Pathological and clinical staging information (TNM system, 8th edition):

Fill in the following table, using both medical charts and pathological reports, to report clinical and pathological staging, respectively. Strive to report TNM prior neoadjuvant therapy.

COLON AND RECTUM STAGING FORM		
CLINICAL <i>Extent of disease before any treatment</i>		PATHOLOGICAL <i>Extent of disease through completion of definitive surgery</i>
	PRIMARY TUMOR (T)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tx	Primary tumor cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Tx
<input type="checkbox"/> T0	No evidence of primary tumor	<input type="checkbox"/> T0
<input type="checkbox"/> Tis	Carcinoma <i>in situ</i> : intraepithelial or invasion of lamina propria*	<input type="checkbox"/> Tis
<input type="checkbox"/> T1	Tumor invades submucosa	<input type="checkbox"/> T1
<input type="checkbox"/> T2	Tumor invades muscularis propria	<input type="checkbox"/> T2
<input type="checkbox"/> T3	Tumor invades through the muscularis propria into pericolorectal tissues	<input type="checkbox"/> T3
<input type="checkbox"/> T4a	Tumor penetrates to the surface of visceral peritoneum**	<input type="checkbox"/> T4a
<input type="checkbox"/> T4b	Tumor directly invades or is adherent to other organs or structures^**	<input type="checkbox"/> T4b
	<i>*Note:</i> This includes cancer cells confined within the glandular basement membrane (intraepithelial) or mucosal lamina propria (intramucosal) with no extension through the muscularis mucosae into the submucosa.	
	<i>^Note:</i> Direct invasion in T4 includes invasion of other organs or other segments of the colorectum as a result of direct extension through the serosa, as confirmed on microscopic examination (for example, invasion of the sigmoid colon by a carcinoma of the caecum) or, for cancers in a retro-peritoneal or subperitoneal location, direct invasion of other organs or structures by virtue of extension beyond	

	the muscularis (i.e., respectively, a tumor on the posterior wall of the descending colon invading the left kidney or lateral abdominal wall; or a mid or distal rectal cancer with invasion of prostate, seminal vesicles, cervix or vagina).	
	**Tumor that is adherent to other organs or structures, grossly, is classified cT4b. However, if no tumor is present in the adhesion, microscopically, the classification pT1-4a depending on the anatomical depth of wall invasion. The V and L classifications should be used to identify the presence of absence of vascular or lymphatic invasion whereas the PN site-specific factor should be used for perineural invasion.	
	REGIONAL LYMPH NODES (N)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Nx	Regional lymph node cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Nx
<input type="checkbox"/> N0	No regional lymph node metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> N0
<input type="checkbox"/> N1	Metastasis in 1 to 3 regional lymph nodes	<input type="checkbox"/> N1
<input type="checkbox"/> N1a	Metastasis in 1 regional lymph node	<input type="checkbox"/> N1a
<input type="checkbox"/> N1b	Metastasis in 2-3 regional lymph nodes	<input type="checkbox"/> N1b
<input type="checkbox"/> N1c	Tumor deposit(s) in the subserosa, mesentery, or non-peritonealised pericolonic or perirectal tissues without regional nodal metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> N1c
<input type="checkbox"/> N2	Metastasis in 4 or more regional lymph nodes	<input type="checkbox"/> N2
<input type="checkbox"/> N2a	Metastasis in 4 to 6 more regional lymph nodes	<input type="checkbox"/> N2a
<input type="checkbox"/> N2b	Metastasis in 7 or more regional lymph nodes	<input type="checkbox"/> N2b
	<i>Note:</i> A satellite peri-tumoral nodule in the pericorectal adipose tissue of a primary carcinoma without histologic evidence of residual lymph node in the nodule may represent discontinuous spread, venous invasion with extra vascular spread (V1/2) or a totally replaced lymph node (N1/2). Replaced nodes should be counted separately as positive nodes in the N category, whereas discontinuous spread or venous invasion should be classified and counted in the Site-Specific Factor category Tumor Deposits (TD).	
	DISTANT METASTASIS (M)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Mx	Distant metastasis cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Mx

<input type="checkbox"/> M0	No distant metastasis (no pathological M0; use clinical M to complete stage group)	<input type="checkbox"/> M0
<input type="checkbox"/> M1	Distant metastasis	<input type="checkbox"/> M1
<input type="checkbox"/> M1a	Metastasis confined to one organ or site (e.g. liver, lung, ovary, non-regional node)	<input type="checkbox"/> M1a
<input type="checkbox"/> M1b	Metastases in more than one organ/site or the peritoneum	<input type="checkbox"/> M1b
If M1, site(s) of metastasis:	

6.5. Comments:

Appendix 7. Clinical Follow-up

Patient information: id number |_|_|_|_|_|_|_|_| initials: _____ (do not enter in database)

Time since diagnosis:	1 year	3 years
Form completed on: By (name):	_ _ / _ _ / _ _ _ _ (DD / MM / YYYY) 	_ _ / _ _ / _ _ _ _ (DD / MM / YYYY)
Source of information (check all that apply):	<input type="checkbox"/> Cancer registry <input type="checkbox"/> Mortality registry/vital statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Death certificates <input type="checkbox"/> Contact with patient or patient's family <input type="checkbox"/> Contact with the physician <input type="checkbox"/> Medical charts <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify:..... <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown	<input type="checkbox"/> Cancer registry <input type="checkbox"/> Mortality registry/vital statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Death certificates <input type="checkbox"/> Contact with patient or patient's family <input type="checkbox"/> Contact with the physician <input type="checkbox"/> Medical charts <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify:..... <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
Vital status: Date last known to be alive or date of death, whichever applies:	<input type="checkbox"/> Alive <input type="checkbox"/> Dead <input type="checkbox"/> Lost to follow-up Day _ _ (1-31) Month _ _ (1-12) Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)	<input type="checkbox"/> Alive <input type="checkbox"/> Dead <input type="checkbox"/> Lost to follow-up Day _ _ (1-31) Month _ _ (1-12) Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)
If alive: Disease status	<input type="checkbox"/> Loco-regional progression <input type="checkbox"/> distant progression <input type="checkbox"/> complete remission <input type="checkbox"/> partial remission <input type="checkbox"/> relapse <input type="checkbox"/> stable <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown	<input type="checkbox"/> Loco-regional progression <input type="checkbox"/> distant progression <input type="checkbox"/> complete remission <input type="checkbox"/> partial remission <input type="checkbox"/> relapse <input type="checkbox"/> stable <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

<p>Date of last news:</p> <p>If Progression (local or distant) or relapse,</p> <p>Method(s) used to confirm the patient's progression disease status</p>	<p>Day _ _ (1-31) Month _ _ (1-12) Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Autopsy <input type="checkbox"/> Biopsy <input type="checkbox"/> Biomarker in liquid biopsy (e.g. tumor marker in blood or urine) <input type="checkbox"/> Blood Draw <input type="checkbox"/> Bone Marrow Aspirate <input type="checkbox"/> Cytology <input type="checkbox"/> Imaging <input type="checkbox"/> Fine needle aspiration <input type="checkbox"/> Laparoscopy <input type="checkbox"/> Surgical Resection <input type="checkbox"/> Other</p>	<p>Day _ _ (1-31) Month _ _ (1-12) Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Autopsy <input type="checkbox"/> Biopsy <input type="checkbox"/> Biomarker in liquid biopsy (e.g. tumor marker in blood or urine) <input type="checkbox"/> Blood Draw <input type="checkbox"/> Bone Marrow Aspirate <input type="checkbox"/> Cytology <input type="checkbox"/> Imaging <input type="checkbox"/> Fine needle aspiration <input type="checkbox"/> Laparoscopy <input type="checkbox"/> Surgical Resection <input type="checkbox"/> Other</p>
<p>If dead:</p> <p>Primary cause of death:</p> <p>Secondary cause of death:</p>	<p>ICD-10 code: _ _ _ _ if available, or select one of the following:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Index cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Other cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Toxicity from treatment used for index cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Infection <input type="checkbox"/> Cardiovascular disease <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify: </p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Unknown</p> <p>ICD-10 code: _ _ _ _ if available, or select one of the following:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Index cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Other cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Toxicity from treatment used for index cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Infection <input type="checkbox"/> Cardiovascular disease <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Unknown</p>	<p>ICD-10 code: _ _ _ _ if available, or select one of the following:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Index cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Other cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Toxicity from treatment used for index cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Infection <input type="checkbox"/> Cardiovascular disease <input type="checkbox"/> Other, specify: </p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Unknown</p> <p>ICD-10 code: _ _ _ _ if available, or select one of the following:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Index cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Other cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Toxicity from treatment used for index cancer <input type="checkbox"/> Infection <input type="checkbox"/> Cardiovascular disease</p>

<p>Distant recurrence 2:</p>	<p>based on AJCC Revision 8</p> <p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 4a <input type="checkbox"/> 4b <input type="checkbox"/> 4c <input type="checkbox"/> 4d</p> <p>rN: <input type="checkbox"/> X</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c</p> <p>rM : <input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1</p> <p>rStage:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I <input type="checkbox"/> IA <input type="checkbox"/> IB <input type="checkbox"/> IC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> II <input type="checkbox"/> IIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> III <input type="checkbox"/> IIIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIIC <input type="checkbox"/> IIID</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> IVA <input type="checkbox"/> IVB <input type="checkbox"/> IVC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Distant recurrence 2:</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Site :.....</p> <p>Please, complete TNM of metastase, based on AJCC Revision 8</p> <p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 4a <input type="checkbox"/> 4b <input type="checkbox"/> 4c <input type="checkbox"/> 4d</p> <p>rN: <input type="checkbox"/> X</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c</p> <p>rM : <input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1</p> <p>rStage:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I <input type="checkbox"/> IA <input type="checkbox"/> IB <input type="checkbox"/> IC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> II <input type="checkbox"/> IIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> III <input type="checkbox"/> IIIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIIC <input type="checkbox"/> IIID</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> IVA <input type="checkbox"/> IVB <input type="checkbox"/> IVC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Distant recurrence 2:</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Site :.....</p>	<p>Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p>Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p>Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p>Site :.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Please, complete TNM of metastase, based on AJCC Revision 8</p> <p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 4a <input type="checkbox"/> 4b <input type="checkbox"/> 4c <input type="checkbox"/> 4d</p> <p>rN: <input type="checkbox"/> X</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c</p> <p>rM : <input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1</p> <p>rStage:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I <input type="checkbox"/> IA <input type="checkbox"/> IB <input type="checkbox"/> IC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> II <input type="checkbox"/> IIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> III <input type="checkbox"/> IIIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIIC <input type="checkbox"/> IIID</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> IVA <input type="checkbox"/> IVB <input type="checkbox"/> IVC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Distant recurrence 2:</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Site :.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Please, complete TNM of metastase, based on AJCC Revision 8</p>
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Distant recurrence 3:	<p>rStage:</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> I <input type="checkbox"/> IA <input type="checkbox"/> IB <input type="checkbox"/> IC <input type="checkbox"/> II <input type="checkbox"/> IIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIC <input type="checkbox"/> III <input type="checkbox"/> IIIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIIC <input type="checkbox"/> IIID <input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> IVA <input type="checkbox"/> IVB <input type="checkbox"/> IVC </p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Distant recurrence 3:</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p>Site :.....</p> <p>Please, complete TNM of metastase, based on AJCC Revision 8</p> <p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 4a <input type="checkbox"/> 4b <input type="checkbox"/> 4c <input type="checkbox"/> 4d </p> <p>rN: <input type="checkbox"/> X</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c </p> <p>rM : <input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1</p> <p>rStage:</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> I <input type="checkbox"/> IA <input type="checkbox"/> IB <input type="checkbox"/> IC <input type="checkbox"/> II <input type="checkbox"/> IIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIC <input type="checkbox"/> III <input type="checkbox"/> IIIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIIC <input type="checkbox"/> IIID <input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> IVA <input type="checkbox"/> IVB <input type="checkbox"/> IVC </p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Distant recurrence 3:</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p>Site :.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Please, complete TNM of metastase, based on AJCC Revision 8</p> <p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d </p>	<p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d <input type="checkbox"/> 4 <input type="checkbox"/> 4a <input type="checkbox"/> 4b <input type="checkbox"/> 4c <input type="checkbox"/> 4d </p> <p>rN: <input type="checkbox"/> X</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c </p> <p>rM : <input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1</p> <p>rStage:</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> I <input type="checkbox"/> IA <input type="checkbox"/> IB <input type="checkbox"/> IC <input type="checkbox"/> II <input type="checkbox"/> IIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIC <input type="checkbox"/> III <input type="checkbox"/> IIIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIIC <input type="checkbox"/> IIID <input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> IVA <input type="checkbox"/> IVB <input type="checkbox"/> IVC </p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Distant recurrence 3:</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p>Site :.....</p> <p>.....</p> <p>Please, complete TNM of metastase, based on AJCC Revision 8</p> <p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d </p>
Distant recurrence 4:	<p>rStage:</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> I <input type="checkbox"/> IA <input type="checkbox"/> IB <input type="checkbox"/> IC <input type="checkbox"/> II <input type="checkbox"/> IIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIC <input type="checkbox"/> III <input type="checkbox"/> IIIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIIC <input type="checkbox"/> IIID <input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> IVA <input type="checkbox"/> IVB <input type="checkbox"/> IVC </p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Distant recurrence 4:</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p>Site :.....</p> <p>Please, complete TNM of metastase, based on AJCC Revision 8</p> <p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d </p>	<p>rT: <input type="checkbox"/> X <input type="checkbox"/> 0</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1a <input type="checkbox"/> 1b <input type="checkbox"/> 1c <input type="checkbox"/> 1d <input type="checkbox"/> 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 2a <input type="checkbox"/> 2b <input type="checkbox"/> 2c <input type="checkbox"/> 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3a <input type="checkbox"/> 3b <input type="checkbox"/> 3c <input type="checkbox"/> 3d </p>

		<p>rM : <input type="checkbox"/> 0 <input type="checkbox"/> 1</p> <p>rStage:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> I <input type="checkbox"/> IA <input type="checkbox"/> IB <input type="checkbox"/> IC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> II <input type="checkbox"/> IIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> III <input type="checkbox"/> IIIA <input type="checkbox"/> IIIB <input type="checkbox"/> IIIC <input type="checkbox"/> IIID</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> IV <input type="checkbox"/> IVA <input type="checkbox"/> IVB <input type="checkbox"/> IVC</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Second primary cancer:</p> <p style="padding-left: 100px;">Day _ _ (1-31)</p> <p style="padding-left: 100px;">Month _ _ (1-12)</p> <p style="padding-left: 100px;">Year _ _ _ _ (4 digits)</p> <p style="padding-left: 100px;">Site (ICD Code) :</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Unknown</p>
<p>For all:</p>	<p>please Fill in "Treatment Since inclusion" Form for more details</p>	<p>Since last follow-up</p> <p>Second line treatment</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Unknown</p> <p>If yes, please Fill in "Treatment Since follow-up" Form for more details</p>
<p>Additional information/comments:</p>		

Treatment Since Inclusion / Treatment Since Follow-up

All treatments post tumor collection in chronological order / Treatments since last follow-up

Treatment type
(Please select all that apply)

- Surgery
- Radiotherapy

- Chemotherapy
- Hormone therapy
- Immunotherapy
- Other Targeted therapy
- Other specify

.....

If Surgery, Start Date

Day |__|__| (1-31)
Month |__|__| (1-12)
Year |__|__|__|__| (4 digits)

Therapeutic intend

- Not applicable
- adjuvant
- curative
- neoadjuvant
- palliative
- concurrent
- unknown

If Radiotherapy, Start Date

Day |__|__| (1-31)
Month |__|__| (1-12)
Year |__|__|__|__| (4 digits)

End Date

Day |__|__| (1-31)
Month |__|__| (1-12)
Year |__|__|__|__| (4 digits)

Therapeutic intend

- Not applicable
- adjuvant
- curative
- neoadjuvant
- palliative
- concurrent
- unknown

Name (s)

.....

If more than one drug with same period, specify all names separated by a semi-colon (;)

Radiation therapy modality

- Photon
- Proton
- Electron
- Heavy Ions

application form

- External
- Internal (including Brachytherapy)

Indicate the number of total fractions delivered

|__|__|

Indicate the total dose in units of Gray (Gy)

|__|__|

Indicate localization site where radiation therapy was administered

- Head
- Head-Neck
- Thorax
- Spine
- Extremities
- Abdomen
- Pelvis
- Lung
- Bone
- Peritoneum
- Brain
- Liver

If Chemotherapy, Name(s)

.....

If more than one drug with same period, specify all names separated by a semi-colon (;)

Dosage Unit

- mg/m²
- IU/m²
- µg/m²
- g/m²
- kg

Indicate total drug dose in units specified in [unit]

|__|__|__|

If more than one drug with same period, then give total amount of doses

If Hormone Therapy, Name(s)

.....

If more than one drug with same period, specify all names separated by a semi-colon (;)

Dosage Unit

- mg/m²
- IU/m²
- µg/m²

g/m²

kg

Indicate total drug dose in units specified in [unit] |__|__|__|

If more than one drug with same period, then give total amount of doses

Appendix 8. ID numbers and barcoded labels

1. Identification of prospectively recruited participants in the Mutographs study

M : Study Mutographs

1-5: cancer type.

1 = colorectal

2 = esophageal squamous

3 = esophageal adenocarcinoma

4 = pancreatic

5 = renal

1-18 : Country code; 1-4 : Center code

Country	Country Code	Center	Center code
Czech Republic	01	Prague	1
Lithuania	02	Vilnius	1
Poland	03	Warsaw	1
		Lodz	2
Russian Federation	04	Moscow	1
Serbia	05	Belgrade	1
United Kingdom	06	Cambridge	1
		Leeds	2
The Gambia	07	Banjul	1
Kenya	08	Eldoret	1
		Thika	2
Morocco	09	Fès	1
South Africa	10	Johannesburg	1
		Cape Town	2
Tanzania	11	Moshi	1
Uganda	12	Kampala	1
		Entebbe	2
Iran	13	Teheran	1

		Gorgan	2
Japan	14	Tokyo	1
Thailand	15	Bangkok	1
		Hat Yai	2
Canada	16	Toronto	1
Brazil	17	Rio de Janeiro	1
		Sao Paulo	2
		Barretos	3
		Porto Alegre	4
Colombia	18	Bogota	1
Argentina	19	Buenos Aires	1
Romania	19 or 23	Bucharest	1
Hungary	20	Budapest	1
Ukraine	21	Kyiv	1
Greece	22	Athens	1
Bulgaria	23	Sofia	1
Pakistan	24	Jamshoro	1

001-999: sequential subject number

Material: Consent Form

Lifestyle Quest

Anthopological Form

Biosample Logsheet

Pathological Form

Follow-up 1-5

EDTA Vacutainer 1-2

WB1-2 (Whole Blood)

PL1-4 (Plasma)

RBC1-4 (Red Blood Cells)

BC1-2 (Buffy Coat)

TB1-3 (Tumor Biopsy)

TR1-3 (Tumor Resection)

NB (Peri-tumor Biopsy)
NR (Peri-tumor Resection)
HB (H&E FFPE Biopsy)
HR (H&E FFPE Resection)
Barcode (without any text) 1-8

Example of IDs:

M1011001-Lifestyle (Colorectal cancer, Czech Republic, Prague, Subject 1, Lifestyle Questionnaire)

M5181001-WB1 (Renal cancer, Colombia, Bogota, Subject 1, Whole blood 1)

Total number of labels per subject: 42

2. Identification of participants recruited through existing/ongoing studies

Existing ID systems in recruiting centres can be readily used if it is impractical to change them. Please contact us beforehand so that we make sure there is no overlap between contributing studies.

Appendix 9. Guidelines for shipment of samples to IARC

The UN committee of Experts (CoE) develops recommended procedures for the transport of all types of dangerous goods except radioactive materials, applicable to all modes of transport. The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) develops recommended procedures for the safe transport of radioactive materials. The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) has used these recommendations as the basis for developing the regulations for the safe transport of dangerous goods by air reported in the *Technical Instructions for the Safe Transport of Dangerous Goods by Air*. The International Air Transport Association (IATA) has developed *Dangerous Goods Regulations* that contains all the requirements of the Technical Instructions. IATA has also included additional requirements, which are more restrictive than the Technical Instructions.

Sample containers

All samples sent to IARC must be in watertight, leak-proof sealed cryotubes with threads inside. It is recommended avoiding use of "Eppendorf" tubes. Before packing for shipment, sample tubes should be checked to ensure that they are tightly closed. If, before packing, the tubes have been contaminated with blood or other biological products, these must be removed with a dilute chlorine bleach solution.

Sample labels

It is recommended using printed and bar-coded labels to facilitate sample identification. Handwritten labels should not be used to avoid misidentification or loss of samples. No personal identifiers should be added to the specimens.

Sample packaging

Sample classification

Given the IATA recommendations, there are two categories of infectious substances.

Category A comprises substances which are transported in a form that, when exposure to them occur, are capable of posing permanent disability, life-threatening, or fatal disease to humans or animals. Category A specimens include, but are not restricted to specimens contaminated by highly pathogenic viruses (Ebola, Hantaan, Marburg, Lassa, etc...) or cultures of viruses such as Dengue, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Hepatitis B Virus (HBV). The proper shipping name for such substances is UN2814: "Infectious substance affecting humans" or UN2900: "Infectious substance affecting animals only".

Category B comprises substances which do not meet the above criteria. Most human specimens such as blood samples, tissues, exfoliated cells or urine, not contaminated by highly pathogenic viruses, will fall into Category B. The proper shipping name for such substances is UN3373: "Biological Substance, Category B".

Biospecimens or derived products that have been specifically treated to neutralize infectious agents, or for which there is a minimal likelihood that pathogens are present, are not subject to these regulations. The proper shipping name for such substances is "Exempt Human (or Animal) Specimen".

References:

- **UNECE (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe)**
UN Recommendations on the Transport of Dangerous Goods. Model Regulations.
http://www.unece.org/trans/danger/publi/unrec/rev14/14files_e.html
- **IATA (International Air Transport Association)**
Dangerous Goods Regulations 2005.
<http://www.iata.org/ps/publications/9052.htm>
- **ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization)**
<http://wdcm.nig.ac.jp/wfcc/new/Documents/icaoAddendum.pdf>
- **WHO (World Health Organization)**
Transport of infectious substances
http://www.who.int/csr/resources/publications/biosafety/WHO_CDS_CSR_LYO_2005_22r%20.pdf

Most biological samples sent to IARC are classified in category B. Specimens from category A should not be sent to IARC except in very exceptional circumstances. Packing instruction for category A are stricter (Declaration for Dangerous Goods, in such case, please contact the IARC investigator and the IARC Biological Resources Manager (caboux@iarc.fr). For category B, it is compulsory applying IATA Packing Instruction 650 which includes the triple packaging system.

Triple packaging system

For Biological Substance, Category B, the packaging must consist of three components according Packing Instruction 650 (Figure 1).

1. a primary receptacle(s)
2. a secondary packaging, and
3. a rigid outer packaging

For liquid substances:

- The primary receptacle must be leakproof and must not contain more than 1 L;
- The secondary packaging must be leakproof. If multiple fragile primary receptacles are placed in a single secondary packaging, they must be either individually wrapped or separated to prevent contact between them;
- Absorbent material must be placed between the primary receptacle and the secondary packaging. The absorbent material, such as cotton wool, must be in sufficient quantity to absorb the entire contents of the primary receptacle(s) so that any release of the liquid substance will not compromise the integrity of the cushioning material or the outer packaging;
- The outer packaging must not contain more than 4 L. This quantity excludes ice, dry ice or liquid nitrogen when used to keep specimens cold.

For solid substances:

- The primary receptacle(s) must be siftproof and must not exceed the outer packaging weight limit;
- The secondary packaging must be siftproof;
- If multiple fragile primary receptacles are placed in a single secondary packaging, they must be either individually wrapped or separated to prevent contact between them;
- The outer packaging must not contain more than 4 kg. This quantity excludes ice, dry ice or liquid nitrogen when used to keep specimens cold.

An itemized list of contents must be enclosed between the secondary packaging and the outer packaging and a separate electronic list sent by e-mail. These documents must be placed in a plastic bag to ensure that the moisture in the box does not blur numbers. Another copy of the list and records should be kept at the consignee centre.

At least one surface of the outer packaging must have a minimum dimension of 100 mm x 100 mm.

Package label

The package (outer shipping package) must be clearly identified and described. An example of labels and marks used for shipment of specimens from category B, UN3373 with dry-ice UN1845 to IARC are in [Annex 1](#).

Substances shipped in refrigerated or frozen form

For frozen samples, a sufficient quantity of dry ice (solid CO₂) must be added. For example, for 3 kg of material travelling for 2 days, 20 kg of dry ice is needed. Ensure that all samples are frozen solid before they are placed in a plastic bag in the dry ice, as a sudden change in temperature may crack the tubes. Dry ice or another refrigerant must be placed outside the secondary packaging. The outer packaging must permit the release of carbon-dioxide gas. If packaged with dry-ice, a class 9 label must be placed on one side of the outer package (See [Annex 1](#)).

Indicate on the box: "**To be kept frozen at -20°**". For customs, specify also: "**NO COMMERCIAL VALUE: MATERIAL FOR SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH**". Make sure that accompanying customs documents are complete.

Shipment conditions

At least one week before the expected day of shipment, the responsible IARC scientist must be informed by e-mail or fax of all details of the impending shipment. **Do not ship samples without having received confirmation** from IARC that the message was received and that the proposed shipment details are acceptable.

All information regarding specimen shipment should be given by e-mail or fax: the name of the Air Company, flight number, date and time of arrival in Lyon, and AirWay Bill Number.

Shipment must be made without delay. If there is a transit time, it should be ensured that the parcel is stored in a cold room. Please send the parcel to Lyon at the beginning of a week, preferably on a Monday; do not allow the shipment to arrive at Lyon Airport on a Friday, weekend or holiday, as customs clearance cannot be processed then.

It is not recommended to hand-carry bio-specimens (infectious substances category A and B), either by a visitor to IARC or by an IARC staff member to an Institute. Carrying these types of specimens may cause considerable problems with customs. The only way to hand-carry biological specimens is to obtain authorization from Air Company and customs (at departure and upon arrival). Please contact IARC responsible persons to obtain all authorizations.

IARC CONTACTS

- When in doubt of category of shipment or exceptional shipment of category A specimens, please contact the IARC investigator and Ms Elodie Caboux, the IARC Biological Resources Manager (caboux@iarc.fr).
- For information on importations, please contact Ms Fabienne Lelong, the Supply Assistant (lelong@iarc.fr).
- For information on exportations, please contact Ms Sophie Servat, the Administrative Assistant (servat@iarc.fr).

[Annex 1:](#)

Consignee:

WHO

OMS

INTERNATIONAL AGENCY FOR RESEARCH ON CANCER
CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE RECHERCHE SUR LE CANCER

25 avenue Tony Garnier
CS 90627 69366 LYON CEDEX 07
France

Attention:

.....

Tel:.....

E-mail :.....

Shipper:

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Responsible person:

.....

Tel:.....

E-mail:.....

BIOLOGICAL SUBSTANCES, CATEGORY B

UN1845 – DRY ICE NET WEIGHT kg

Appendix 10. Processing of tissues for routine pathology examination

Macroscopic description, sectioning and sampling of the resection specimen should be done based on standardized pathology protocols. FFPE blocks should be prepared following standard procedures (included below). Routine protocols of each centre may be used after adjustment and verification with the standard protocols. FFPE blocks and sections can be stored at room temperature.

1. Fixation

1.1. Fixation of tissue should be undertaken as soon as possible. Optimally, tissue should be fixed within 4 hours from resection.

1.2. Perform fixation at room temperature (25° C).

1.3. Fix tissue in with 10% neutral buffered formalin or other appropriate fixatives for 2-24 hours at room temperature. Fixation time depends on the volume of the tissue. Make sure there is enough fixative to cover tissues. Fixative volume should be 10 times of tissue volume. It is important that the fixative is buffered to keep the neutral pH of the fixative.

2. Preparation of FFPE blocks

2.1. Once fixation has occurred, trim a representative area of approximately 3-5 mm thickness and place in embedding cassettes, along with an accompanying label with sequential code following local laboratory practice.

2.2. Process for paraffin embedding schedule as follow:

- 80% ethanol, two changes, 1 hour each
- 95% ethanol, two changes, 1 hour each
- 100% ethanol, three changes, 1 hour each
- Toluene, xylene or xylene substitute (i.e., Clear Rite 3), three changes, 1 hour each
- Paraffin wax (54-58 °C), two changes, 1.5 hour each
- Embed tissue into paraffin blocks; to make a complete bond between infiltrating and embedding wax, both must be liquid. The solid block is hard and allows thin sectioning of the tissue.

3. Preparing of sections

3.1. Trim paraffin block as necessary and cut at 3-5µm, using a rotary microtome.

3.2. Place obtained paraffin ribbons in water bath at about 40-45°C.

3.3. Mount sections onto slides.

3.4. Allow sections to air dry for 30 minutes and then bake in 37-45°C oven overnight. They may be dried at 60°C for 15 minutes if they are required the same day.

4. Staining

- 4.1. Deparaffinise sections in 2-3 changes of toluene or xylene, 10 minutes each.
- 4.2. Hydrate in 2 changes of 100% ethanol for 3 minutes each, 95% and 80% ethanol for 1 minute each. Then rinse in distilled water.
- 4.3. Proceed with standard H&E staining protocol, carefully checking the time to avoid over fixation at each step.
- 4.4. Dehydrate, clear and mount.

5. Storage

- 5.1. FFPE blocks and sections mounted on slides can be stored at room temperature. Prevent exposure of blocks to sun or extreme temperature variance.
- 5.2. Store blocks in moisture resistant cardboard boxes or plastic storage boxes.
- 5.3. Enter storage location in a computerized database system.

Appendix 11. Tumor tissue pathology evaluation form

A. GENERAL INFORMATION

Specimen Number: Pathologist full name:

Date of review (DD/MM/YYYY) : |_|_|/|_|_|/|_|_|_|_|

1. Type of specimen reviewed:

- Endoscopic biopsy
- Polypectomy (for colon cancers)
- Resection

B. HISTOMORPHOLOGY

1. FFPE_H&E stained slide:

KIDNEY	OESOPHAGUS	PANCREAS	COLORECTUM
<i>TUMOR TYPE</i>			
<input type="checkbox"/> Insufficient for diagnosis			
<input type="checkbox"/> No significant pathological changes			
<input type="checkbox"/> No invasive tumor			
<input type="checkbox"/> Clear cell RCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Ductal adenocarcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma
<input type="checkbox"/> Papillary RCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Squamous cell carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Colloid carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Mucinous adenocarcinoma
<input type="checkbox"/> Chromophobe RCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Signet-ring cell carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Signet-ring cell adenocarcinoma
<input type="checkbox"/> RCC, unclassified	<input type="checkbox"/> Basaloid SCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Squamous cell carcinoma
<input type="checkbox"/> Others (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Verrucous SCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Hepatoid carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma
	<input type="checkbox"/> Spindle cell (squamous) carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma
	<input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma

	<input type="checkbox"/> Others (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Others (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Serrated adenocarcinoma
			<input type="checkbox"/> Others (specify)
COMMENT: _____	COMMENT: _____	COMMENT: _____	COMMENT: _____

TUMOR DIFFERENTIATION GRADE ^{1,2}

<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable
<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 (WD)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 (WD)	<input type="checkbox"/> Low grade (WD to MD)
<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 (MD)	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 (MD)	<input type="checkbox"/> High grade (PD to UD)
<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 (PD)	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 (PD)	<input type="checkbox"/> Cannot be assessed
<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 (UD)	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 (UD)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Cannot be assessed	
<input type="checkbox"/> Sarcomatoid feature			
<input type="checkbox"/> Rhabdoid feature			

¹ The provided grading system for the pancreatic ductal adenocarcinomas (PDADC) is based on CAP 2016 guidelines. If WHO grading system is used for grading please specify.

² WHO 2010 grading system for PDADC:

Grade 1: Well differentiated glands; intensive mucin production; 5 mitoses/10HPF; little nuclear polymorphism.

Grade 2: Moderately differentiated glands; irregular mucin production; 6-10 mitoses/10HPF; moderate nuclear polymorphism.

Grade 3: Poorly differentiated glands; abortive mucin production; >10 mitoses/10HPF; marked nuclear polymorphism.

2. Frozen section_H&E stained slide:

KIDNEY	OESOPHAGUS	PANCREAS	COLORECTUM
TUMOR TYPE ¹			
<input type="checkbox"/> Insufficient for diagnosis			
<input type="checkbox"/> No significant pathological changes			
<input type="checkbox"/> No invasive tumor			
<input type="checkbox"/> Clear cell RCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Ductal adenocarcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenocarcinoma

<input type="checkbox"/> Papillary RCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Squamous carcinoma cell	<input type="checkbox"/> Colloid carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Mucinous adenocarcinoma
<input type="checkbox"/> Chromophobe RCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Signet-ring cell carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Signet-ring cell adenocarcinoma
<input type="checkbox"/> RCC, unclassified	<input type="checkbox"/> Basaloid SCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Squamous cell carcinoma
<input type="checkbox"/> Others (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Verrucous SCC	<input type="checkbox"/> Hepatoid carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Adenosquamous carcinoma
	<input type="checkbox"/> Spindle (squamous) carcinoma cell	<input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma
	<input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Undifferentiated carcinoma	<input type="checkbox"/> Medullary carcinoma
	<input type="checkbox"/> Others (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Others (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Serrated adenocarcinoma
			<input type="checkbox"/> Others (specify)
COMMENT : _____	COMMENT : _____	COMMENT : _____	COMMENT : _____

TUMOR DIFFERENTIATION GRADE²

<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable	<input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable
<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 (WD)	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 (WD)	<input type="checkbox"/> Low grade (WD to MD)
<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 (MD)	<input type="checkbox"/> 2 (MD)	<input type="checkbox"/> High grade (PD to UD)
<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 (PD)	<input type="checkbox"/> 3 (PD)	<input type="checkbox"/> Cannot be assessed
<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 (UD)	<input type="checkbox"/> 4 (UD)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Cannot be assessed	<input type="checkbox"/> Cannot be assessed	
<input type="checkbox"/> Sarcomatoid feature			
<input type="checkbox"/> Rhabdoid feature			

¹Some tumor types might be difficult to be diagnosed/confirmed on frozen section. In such cases, please provide your most compatible diagnosis in the comment.

²For the PDADC, specify the grading system (referable to footnotes 1&2 in section B).

Urothelial

*TUMOR TYPE*¹

- Insufficient for diagnosis
- Urothelial carcinoma in situ
- Non-invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma, low grade
- Non-invasive papillary urothelial carcinoma, high grade
- Papillary urothelial neoplasm of low malignant potential
- Urothelial papilloma
- Inverted urothelial papilloma
- Infiltrating urothelial carcinoma
- Infiltrating urothelial carcinoma variant, specify
- SCC
- Adenocarcinoma
- Others (specify)

COMMENT : _____

*TUMOR DIFFERENTIATION GRADE*²

- Not applicable
- Low grade (WD to MD)
- High grade (PD to UD)
- Cannot be assessed

C. TISSUE ELEMENTS

SH1	
Total size (area mm ²): _ _ _ _ · _ _ _ _	
TISSUE ELEMENTS	%
1 – Tumor	_ _ _ _
2 – Non-tumor	_ _ _ _
3 - Inflammation	_ _ _ _
4 – Necrosis	_ _ _ _
Comment: _____	

<p>Recommended approach</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Exclude</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Include, routine protocol</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Include after enrichment</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Macrodissection</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><input type="checkbox"/> LCM</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Include whole biopsy</p> <p>Comment: _____</p>
--

SH1M	
Total size (area mm ²): _ _ _ _ · _ _ _ _	
TISSUE ELEMENTS	%
1 – Tumor	_ _ _ _
2 – Non-tumor	_ _ _ _
3 - Inflammation	_ _ _ _
4 – Necrosis	_ _ _ _
Comment: _____	

<p>Recommended approach</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Exclude</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Include, routine protocol</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Include whole biopsy</p>

<input type="checkbox"/> SH2 <input type="checkbox"/> SH2M Total size (area mm²): _ _ _ _ · _ _ _ _	
TISSUE ELEMENTS	%
1 – Tumor	_ _ _ _
2 – Non-tumor	_ _ _ _
3 – Inflammation	_ _ _ _
4 – Necrosis	_ _ _ _
Comment: _____	
Final Decision <input type="checkbox"/> Exclude <input type="checkbox"/> OK for DNA extraction	

<input type="checkbox"/> SH3 <input type="checkbox"/> SH3M Total size (area mm²): _ _ _ _ · _ _ _ _	
TISSUE ELEMENTS	%
1 – Tumor	_ _ _ _
2 – Non-tumor	_ _ _ _
3 – Inflammation	_ _ _ _
4 – Necrosis	_ _ _ _
Comment: _____	
Final Decision <input type="checkbox"/> Exclude <input type="checkbox"/> OK for DNA extraction	

Appendix 12. Core set of variables required

(without which a case is not eligible for inclusion)

Variable	Variable description	Relevant cancer site
General	Sex	All
	Age	All
Body size	BMI at diagnosis, or other recent measure of BMI	Oesophageal adenocarcinoma
		Kidney
		Pancreas
		Colorectal
Medical History	Diabetes	Oesophageal adenocarcinoma
		Kidney
		Pancreas
		Colorectal
	Hypertension	Kidney
	Type of delivery at birth	Colorectal
	Breastfeeding	Colorectal
Antibiotic use	Colorectal	
Tobacco	Current cigarette smoking	All
	Past cigarette smoking	All
Alcohol	Current alcohol consumption	All
	Past alcohol consumption	All
Hot drinks	This is somewhat centre dependent, although specific questions that will allow for identification of those who consume local beverages at a hot temperature are required	Squamous oesophageal
Diet	Red meat consumption	Colorectal cancer
	Processed meat consumption	Colorectal cancer

Appendix 13. Interview guidelines

GENERAL RULES

1. Before interview starts, please read the "Informed Consent" form and obtain the subject's signature, if possible, to the six requested study components. Note that if the patient does not give consent to any of the first 5 components (any except 'Sharing of genetic research data with your doctor') it will not be feasible to include the patient in the *mutographs* study.
2. Questions must be asked, as far as possible, as they are written.
3. Questionnaires must be filled in with a pencil and written clearly.
4. The columns should be filled in justified to the right.
5. If you do not succeed in getting an answer or estimation, the columns should be filled in with 9 (or 99 where two-digit answers are possible).
6. Try not to influence the subject's reply to any extent but read each question with calm and self-confidence. However, if you notice inconsistencies between responses, try to clarify.
7. If the patient is too tired to continue then the interview may be halted for a break to occur.
8. The local coordinator may add more questions to the questionnaire. If so, they have to be added at the end of the corresponding section.
9. The local coordinator may add more values for some items. E.g., another ethnic group or a code for multiple answers.
10. All local codes assigned must be provided with the final dataset.
11. The accuracy of the questionnaire information is of absolute importance to the success of the study. The local coordinator should review all questionnaires for completeness and lack of inconsistencies. They also have the option to revisit any patient to confirm interview questions, should this be necessary.

Appendix 14. Standard Operational Procedure for the quality of FFPE slides

1. Introduction

The purpose of this SOP is to describe a harmonized approach to assure the quality of the glass slides that are prepared from formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) slides.

2. Objective

To define the procedure and to establish the basic quality guidelines to prepare glass slides from FFPE tissues. These slides will be prepared and stored by the participating institutions until further shipment to IARC for scanning.

3. Processing protocol

Step	Protocol	Image
<p>1. <u>If preparing new slides only for the purpose of shipment:</u></p>	<p>Select the FFPE block that has a big piece of tissue.</p> <p>To avoid heterogeneous surface, put only one section per slide when the tissue is big and not more than two sections for biopsies.</p> <p>Put the sections in the middle of slide. Avoid placing the sections at the edge of slide.</p> <p>Use glass slides with the standard size and thickness. Avoid thick slides.</p> <p>Use standard coverslips, preferably 24x40 or 24x50mm. Try to avoid 22x22 mm ones even for biopsies.</p> <p>Clean up the extra glue that may cover the surface or edges of the coverslip.</p> <p>No air bubble should be seen under coverslip. If so, remove the cover slip and repeat the procedure.</p> <p>After putting coverslip, let the slides to be fully dried on a flat surface and in a horizontal position. Do not put the slides immediately after insertion of coverslip into the box to avoid slippage of the glue.</p>	

<p>2. <u>If using the slides from your archive:</u></p>	<p>Broken slides are not acceptable and will prevent sharp scanning. Avoid repairing by gluing the broken pieces. Use another one.</p>	
	<p>If anything written on the surface of the slide anywhere, clean it up with alcohol before shipment.</p>	
	<p>Thick slides, thick coverslips, tissue sections at the edge of slide, dirty slides, slides with any kind of written things, prevent homogenous and sharp scanning. Avoid them!</p>	
<p>3. Slide identification</p>	<p>Stick IARC labels on the top of the slides in the dedicated area, do not put them on the back of the slides. Do not write on the slides.</p> <p>Use only printed labels with barcode to identify the slides, preferably the ones provided by IARC. Ask us to provide your printed labels if necessary.</p>	
<p>4. <u>Slide shipment</u></p>	<p>Slides should be organized in a storage box and shipped in a parcel at ambient temperature.</p> <p>Choose a proper size of slide box based on the number of slides to ship (for example, don't use a 100-box to ship only 10 slides).</p> <p>Do not store two slides back to back with no space between.</p> <p>After filling the box and before closure, cover the entire area of the arranged slides with a piece of tissue paper, simply a napkin. This helps to stabilize the slides in the box and protects them from breakage.</p>	

	Lock the box, tape it to secure the lid and to prevent opening it during shipment.	
--	--	--

Appendix 15. Sanger Institute's shipment procedures

TA_GDL_0001 Guidelines for submission of DNA to WTSI v1

Guidelines for shipment of DNA to the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute

Unless otherwise agreed, IARC is responsible for shipping eligible germline/tumor DNA pairs to the Sanger Institute.

1. Rack Type

We will send via FedEx:

- FluidX 0.7ml externally threaded 2D barcoded tube rack (Part number 68-0702-12 – pre-capped, pre-racked)

A maximum number of 95 samples will be supplied in any one rack; H12 should be left empty for a QC processing control. If less than 95 samples are being submitted the rack should be filled in column order.

2. Sample Manifests

Accompanying each unique rack of FluidX 0.7ml externally threaded 2D barcoded tubes will be a sample manifest.

The minimum information is required to add the samples to our system are those columns highlighted in bright yellow and includes the following:

1. Material (column J)
2. Species (column I)
3. Volume Supplied (column L)
4. Unique donor ID (column Q)
5. Gender (column S)
6. Has this sample been sent before (column R)
7. Age at Diagnosis (column U)
8. Tissue type (column Y)
9. Specimen Type (column Z)

Columns F, G, H will have been auto populated with the scanned tube and rack numbers. Position H12 should please be left empty for a QC control, which will be added at WTSI.

Please ensure that the unique donor information corresponds to the correct unique human readable barcode located on the side of the tube and that the tube is correctly positioned in the rack.

3. Quantity of DNA required

3.1. Standard pipeline (6 cycles of PCR)

Quantity of DNA is dependent upon processing requirements. A minimum of 200ng of DNA is required for whole genome sequencing.

It is advisable however to send additional material in case repeat work or additional workflows are required. This prevents any additional costs or time delays due to shipment of new aliquots and subsequent checks against the original material to ensure they belong to the same individual.

Human DNA Shipping Requirements	Total µg Required	Ideal Volume (µl)	Ideal Concentration (ng/µl)	Minimum volume (µl)
	1.5	75	20	25

The above table shows ideal volume and concentrations; the minimum volume must be strictly adhered to allow automated processing of samples. A range in concentrations up to 300ng/ul can be processed. Nevertheless, it is highly recommended to not exceed 40ng/ul to avoid an additional normalization step (if a high variability of concentrations is present across the rack/plate, multiple rounds of quantification will be necessary and therefore incur a higher cost). QC utilizes 1000nl of sample therefore higher concentration supplied will result in a higher amount used during the QC process.

3.2. Bespoke pipeline (flexible number of PCR)

Similar to the standard pipeline but with the ability to increase the number of PCR cycles to compensate for lower DNA input:

50-100ng: may work

100-200ng: likely to be successful

Important: samples for the bespoke pipeline must be sent on different plates. Reach to contact for more details.

4. Sample Storage

Any remaining stock DNA samples not required for processing will be stored by WTSI at -20°C for the duration of the projects or returned to IARC as agreed by the sample custodian and as outlined in the HMDMC approval documents. Any retention beyond this is reviewed in discussion with the sample custodian.

Any daughter samples generated internally from stock to support the service provision will be stored in Sample Management for 3 months and then destroyed. **If an alternative approach to these samples is required this must be proactively flagged to Sample Management on submission.**

5. Contact Details and Shipping Address

cgp-sample@sanger.ac.uk